

Status and distribution of the small Travancore flying squirrel (*Petinomys fuscocapillus fuscocapillus*) and the large brown flying squirrel (*Petaurista philippensis*) in the Western Ghats.

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THE STATUS AND DISTRIBUTION OF THE SMALL TRAVANCORE FLYING SQUIRREL (*PETINOMYS FUSCOCAPILLUS FUSCOCAPILLUS*) AND THE LARGE BROWN FLYING SQUIRREL (*PETAURISTA PHILIPPENSIS*) IN THE WESTERN GHATS.

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COVER PAGE

Photo descriptions :

1. Aralam Wildlife Sanctuary.
2. *P. philippensis* in Tadoba Wildlife Sanctaury.
3. Small Travancore flying squirrel, Thattekad Zoo.
4. Small Travancore flying squirrel, Thattekad Zoo.

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1. Robin Vijayan
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- 3 & 4. Nandini Rajamani.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iii
ABSTRACT	v
CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION	1
CHAPTER 2. BACKGROUND	3
2.1 <i>Petinomys fuscocapillus fuscocapillus</i>	3
2.2 <i>Petaurista philippensis</i>	4
CHAPTER 3. STUDY AREA	6
CHAPTER 4. METHODS	9
4.1 Data Collection	9
4.2 Data Analysis	10
CHAPTER 5. DISTRIBUTION AND HABITAT PREFERENCES OF FLYING SQUIRRELS	11
5.1 Results	
5.1.1 Distribution of flying squirrels	11
5.1.2 Habitat Types	17
5.1.2a Vegetation types and encounter rate	17
5.1.2b Altitude and encounter rate	18
5.1.3 Forest structure: Characteristics and Use by flying squirrels	19
5.1.3a Tree height	19
5.1.3b Tree girth	21
5.1.3c Distance to nearest neighbor (a measure of density)	22
5.2 Discussion	22
CHAPTER 6. BEHAVIOR	26
6.1 Results	26
6.2 Discussion	28
CHAPTER 7. HUNTING PRESSURES AND LOCAL AWARENESS	30
CHAPTER 8. THE DISTRIBUTION OF FLYING SQUIRRELS IN THE WESTERN GHATS: AN ANALYSIS	33
CHAPTER 9. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	35
PLATE 1: PHOTOGRAPHS	36
PLATE 2: PHOTOGRAPHS	37
LITERATURE CITED	38
APPENDIX 1.	43
APPENDIX 2.	46
APPENDIX 3.	61
APPENDIX 4.	62

LIST OF MAPS

<i>Map no.</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Page no.</i>
1	Study Area located in the Western Ghats, India.	6
2	Sites surveyed in the Western Ghats of Kerala and Tamil Nadu	8
3	Distribution of <i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i> in the Western Ghats of Kerala & Tamil Nadu.	15
4	Distribution of <i>P. philippensis</i> in the Western Ghats of Kerala and Tamil Nadu.	16

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Page no.</i>
5.1	Encounter rates of flying squirrels in Protected and Less Protected areas.	12
5.2	Encounter rates of flying squirrels across different vegetation types.	17
5.3	Encounter rates of flying squirrels across different altitudes. (Mean \pm S.E.)	18
5.4	Height of trees in plots where flying squirrels were and were not sighted.	19
5.5	Girth of trees in plots where flying squirrels were and were not sighted.	19
5.6	Regressing height occupied by <i>P. philippensis</i> against height of the tree.	20
5.7	Regressing height occupied by <i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i> against height of the tree.	20
5.8	Tree strata utilized by flying squirrels.	20
5.9	Girth wise distribution of trees in plots.	21
6.1	Percentage frequency of observed flying squirrel activities at first observation.	26
6.2	Number of flying squirrels sighted over time.	27
6.3	Activity patterns of flying squirrels.	27

LIST OF TABLES

<i>Table no.</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Page no.</i>
2.1	Comparative summary of description of the two species.	5
3.1	List of study sites, vegetation types surveyed, and effort per area visited.	7
5.1	Encounter rates (Mean \pm S.D.) of the two species of flying squirrels in different sampling sites.	11
5.2	Encounter rates of the two species of flying squirrels in different vegetation types within each sampling site.	13
5.3	Encounter rates of the two species of flying squirrels in different altitude zones within each sampling site.	14
6.1	Description of hollows of <i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i> .	28
7.1	Reports of hunting pressures of flying squirrels in areas surveyed.	30
A1.1	Sampling effort (km walked) across vegetation types and survey sites.	43
A1.2	Sampling effort (km walked) across altitude zones and survey sites.	44
A1.3	Sampling effort (km walked) across vegetation types and altitude zones.	44
A1.4	Reports of hunting pressures in different locations.	45
A4	Other nocturnal mammals sighted during night transects.	62

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ABSTRACT

A survey of the two species of flying squirrels *P. f. fuscocapillus* and *P. philippensis* was conducted in the Western Ghats of Tamil Nadu and Kerala for a period of four months, between February 2000 and May 2000. *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered on 11 occasions and *P. philippensis* was encountered on 199 occasions.

P. f. fuscocapillus was encountered only in Evergreen and Moist deciduous forests up to an elevation of 900m, and was encountered more in Evergreen forest (Encounter rate : 0.12 squirrels/ km \pm 0.069 S.E., n= 25 walks) than in Moist Deciduous forest (Encounter rate: 0.03 squirrels / km \pm 0.028, n=19 walks). *P. philippensis* was encountered over a broader range of habitat types and altitude, and was encountered most in Moist Deciduous forest (Encounter rate: 1.60 squirrels/ km \pm 0.655 S.E., n=19 walks), followed by Plantations (Encounter rate: 1.36 squirrels/ km \pm 0.486 S.E., n=8) and Evergreen forests (Encounter rate: 1.6 squirrels/ km \pm 0.286 S.E., n=25). Neither species was encountered in Dry Forests. The encounter rate of *P. f. fuscocapillus* was significantly lower than the encounter rate of *P. philippensis* in both Evergreen forest (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=n_2=25$, $z=-4.893$, $p \leq 0.001$) and Moist Deciduous forests (Mann Whitney U Test, $n_1=n_2=19$, $z=-4.016$, $p \leq 0.0001$). The encounter rate of *P. philippensis* (1.33 squirrels/ km \pm 0.726 S.E., n=18 walks) was significantly greater than the encounter rate of *P. f. fuscocapillus* (0.69 squirrels/ km \pm 0.033 S.E., n=18 walks) in the elevation range 0-500 m (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=n_2=18$, $z=1.605$, $p < 0.05$).

Habitat characteristics were measured at sites where flying squirrels were and were not sighted, and analysis of the variables revealed that stands where flying squirrels were found contained taller and larger trees than stands where they were not found. The height of trees in stands where *P. philippensis* was sighted was significantly higher than the height of trees in stands where it was not sighted (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1= 474$, $n_2= 207$, $z=-3.50$, $p < 0.001$). The height of the tree utilised by both species of flying squirrels was also greater than the surrounding trees (*P. f. fuscocapillus*: Mann Whitney U Test, $n_1= 56$, $n_2= 14$, $z = -3.25$, $p < 0.001$; *P. philippensis*: Mann Whitney U test, $n_1= 264$, $n_2= 93$, $z = -9.16$, $p < 0.001$). The height occupied by the two flying squirrels differed significantly (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1= 18$, $n_2= 126$, $z=2.152$, $p=0.036$) and *P. philippensis* was encountered higher (18.86 m \pm 0.516 S.E, n=126) on the tree than *P. f. fuscocapillus* (18.27 m \pm 1.096 S.E, n=18).

The girths of trees in stands where no flying squirrels were sighted (1.07 m \pm 0.06 S.E., n=225 trees) were significantly lower than the girths of trees where they were sighted (*P. philippensis*: Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=475$, $n_2=225$, $z=-5.54$, $p < 0.001$; *P. f. fuscocapillus*: Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=70$, $n_2=225$, $z=-2.14$, $p < 0.05$). The girths of trees utilised by both species of flying squirrels were significantly greater than the girths of other trees in the plot (*P. f. fuscocapillus*: Mann Whitney U Test, $n_1=56$, $n_2=14$, $z=-3.39$, $p < 0.01$, *P. philippensis*: Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=406$, $n_2=10$, $z=-9.40$, $p < 0.01$). The distance from the tree the squirrels were sighted on to the nearest neighbour was used as a measure of relative density of the stand. The distance to the nearest neighbour in plots centred around sightings of *P. philippensis* was significantly greater than in the random plots (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1= 45$, $n_2=97$, $z=-1.96$, $p < 0.05$).

The results of this survey suggest that the choice of habitat by the two species of flying squirrels might be influenced by characteristics of the habitat, like the size and density of trees. In the stand. The reasons for choice of larger trees might be a) larger trees are better food sources, b) larger trees provide more nest hollows, c) larger trees might enable longer and therefore more economical glides. While *P. philippensis* was seen to prefer less dense stands, the smaller species *P. f. fuscocapillus* was seen to prefer more dense stands. This might be influenced by the gliding capabilities of the animals.

1. INTRODUCTION

Flying squirrels (Rodentia: Sciuridae: Petauristinae) are nocturnal gliding mammals, and occur in 12 genera and 43 species. From Asia as a centre of speciation, they have spread to North America, northern Asia and Europe (Eisenberg 1981). While only one species of flying squirrel is found in Europe and north Asia, and two species in North America, all other species are confined to Asia and species richness reaches its peak in the Southeast Asian countries (Lee and Liao 1998). Eleven species are found in India, most of which are concentrated in the Himalayan and Northeast regions, while the Western Ghats remains depauperate with only two species found along its stretch.

The Small Travancore Flying Squirrel (*Petinomys fuscocapillus fuscocapillus*) and the Large Brown Flying Squirrel (*Petaurista philippensis*) are the only two species of gliding mammals found in the Western Ghats, South India (Prater 1971, Ashraf *et al* 1993).

The subspecies *Petinomys fuscocapillus fuscocapillus* is endemic to the forests of the Western Ghats (Kurup 1989). The species is rare (Xavier *et al* 1996), and its distribution being restricted to certain forests (Hutton 1949), it is one of the lesser-known species of flying squirrels in India. *Petaurista philippensis* has a broader distribution and occurs in most of the forests of peninsular India (Prater 1971, Agarwal and Chakraborty 1979, Wilson and Reeder 1993).

There is an urgent need to divert attention and funds to the study of these two species, and this need stems from two causes; a) lack of knowledge of the ecology and behaviour of the species, and incomplete distribution records; and, b) the conservation status of the species, and the rapid rate of forest cover loss.

Little is known of *P. f. fuscocapillus* in the Western Ghats, and there are no accounts of its ecology and behaviour. Though *P. philippensis* is relatively better studied, there exist no detailed records of its current distribution in the Western Ghats. Flying squirrels represent one of the least known mammals in the world. While the flying squirrels of the temperate regions have been relatively better studied, there exists a significant gap in knowledge of species distribution and ecology in the Oriental region (Lee *et al* 1986). Though there exist 11 species of flying squirrels in India, there has been little intensive research on them.

The conservation status of *P. f. fuscocapillus* has recently been assessed by the 2000 IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Hilton-Taylor 2000) as **Vulnerable** on the basis of its restricted distribution and the threats to its habitat. The Western Ghats is under increasing human pressure, and there has been a loss of over 25.6% of the total forest cover over the past 22 years (Jha *et al* 2000). Human disturbances gradually change the forest structure and composition and can have a deleterious effect on arboreal mammals (Sunderraj and Johnsingh 2001). Construction of roads, conversion of forested areas to plantations and other developmental activities that destroy or alter the habitat are known to not only affect the population size and dispersal ability of the flying squirrels but may also result in the invasion of competitors, predators and pathogens (Weigl *et al* 1999).

Disappearing forest cover and the exploitation of *P. f. fuscocapillus* for its pelt and flesh, as has been seen in certain parts of Kerala (Xavier *et al* 1996, 1998) are some threats that have adversely affected the species. Though *P. philippensis* is not currently at risk, the effect of such habitat loss and disturbances on populations of *P. philippensis* is unclear.

Knowledge of occurrence and abundance of flying squirrels is necessary to assess their conservation status and is a prerequisite for the design of conservation strategies (Lee and Liao 1998). This study aimed at providing baseline data on the distribution of *P. f. fuscocapillus* and *P. philippensis*, documenting the associated habitat characteristics, and at understanding the problems peculiar to the species.

The objectives of the study were:

- i) to document the occurrence of *P. f. fuscocapillus* and *P. philippensis* across various habitat types.

- ii) to establish the range of *P. f. fuscocapillus* and *P. philippensis* in the forests of Kerala and Tamil Nadu in the Western Ghats.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 *Petinomys fuscocapillus fuscocapillus* (Jerdon 1847)

The genus *Petinomys* (dwarf flying squirrels) consists of seven species that have a combined range from China, southward through the Malay States, Tennaserim, Sumatra, Borneo, Java, Ceylon and Southern India. Nowak (1991) describes this genus as being found only up to an elevation of 1210 m, though certain species are found to occur up to elevations of 1350 m and 1700 m (Payne *et al* 1985). Most species of *Petinomys* are reported to occur in tall and secondary forests (Payne *et al* 1985).

Petinomys fuscocapillus is restricted in distribution to South India and Sri Lanka, with *P. f. fuscocapillus* occurring in south India and *P. f. layardi* occurring in Sri Lanka (Prater 1971, Wilson and Reeder 1993). The genus is disjunct in distribution, with all other species being found in Southeast Asia. (Kurup 1990). *Petinomys fuscocapillus fuscocapillus* is classified in Schedule I of the Indian Wildlife (Protection) Act and is listed as Vulnerable in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Animals 2000.

Described by Jerdon in 1847, the sub species has been collected only thrice, the last being by Kurup (1989) in Central Kerala. *P. f. fuscocapillus* has not been intensively studied since it was taxonomically identified, with the only studies being scattered reports on description (Blanford 1881; Ellerman 1961), body size, measurements, gut contents (Xavier *et al* 1996, Xavier *et al* 1998) and occurrence (Wroughton 1919, Hutton 1949, Menon 1962, 1964, 1965, Prater 1971, Srinivasan 1977, Ashraf *et al* 1993, Balakrishnan and Xavier 1995, Umaphathy and Kumar 2000a).

P. f. fuscocapillus has been recorded in Tamil Nadu from the Nilgiris (Prater 1971), the High Wavy Mountains (Hutton 1949) and the Anamalais (Hutton 1949, Ashraf *et al* 1993, Umaphathy and Kumar 2000a), and it has been recorded in the forests of Travancore (Wroughton 1919, Prater 1971, Kurup 1989) and the Malabar Coast (Wroughton 1919) in Kerala.

No specific population estimates are available for the species, though it is thought to occur at lower densities than the Large Brown Flying Squirrel (Hutton 1949, Ashraf *et al* 1993, Balakrishnan and Xavier 1995, Xavier *et al* 1998). Elimination of low altitude moist deciduous and semi Evergreen forests in the Idukki, Pattanamthitta, Kottayam, Kollam and Thiruvanthapuram districts of Kerala is thought to have affected populations of *P. f. fuscocapillus* (Xavier *et al.* 1998). Recent studies (Kurup 1989, Umaphathy and Kumar 2000a) have however, recorded the species in forest fragments and in plantations raising questions about its tolerance to disturbance.

The species is known by the local name *iliparan* or *eliparan* or *poomparan* in Kerala.

Description of the species

Adapted from Ellerman (1961) and Sterndale (1884):

A medium sized (size in Table 2.1) flying squirrel with thick fur and a broad long, feather shaped tail, the tail in one specimen measuring longer than the head and body. Four fingers on the hand, the fourth being longest. Foot with five toes, of normal proportions, the hallux being the shortest, the sole quite naked with six plantar pads. A pencil of long black hairs is present besides the ears.

Colour: Dorsal surface mostly reddish brown, the sides darker than the middle of the back, and the underfur dark. Two-thirds of the base of the hair is dusky ashy in colour, and the remainder reddish-brown with a black tip. The parachute is dark brown washed with a pale brown, and the edge is a pale yellow. Feet pale yellowish brown. The tail is very bushy, and not distichous in the adult though sometimes partially so in the young, it is sometimes yellowish brown or dusky brown, especially in the latter half, the undersurface being pale brown and passing into brown at the base. Tail with a central line of blackish hairs through most of its length, and lightish brown on either side of this. Underside yellowish white extending to the cheeks and under-lip. The lateral fur margining the membrane is rufous in colour. *P. f. fuscocapillus* is distinguished from *P. f. layardi* by the colour of

the underside, which is white in *P. f. fuscocapillus* and grey in *P. f. layardi*. Cheeks of *P. f. fuscocapillus* are white, washed with yellow.

2.2 *Petaurista philippensis* (Elliot 1939)

The genus *Petaurista* comprises the giant flying squirrels which occur in the tropical and sub-tropical zones of southern Asia from the western Himalayas, northeastern China, Japan and Formosa, southward to Ceylon, Sumatra, Java, Borneo, and small adjacent islands (Wilson and Reeder 1993). *Petaurista* is the most well studied genus of all the flying squirrels found in Asia (Lee and Liao 1998), with most research conducted in Japan (Ando and Imaizumi 1982, Ando and Shiraishi 1983, 1984; Ando *et al* 1983, 1984, Baba *et al* 1982, Kawamichi 1997) and Taiwan (Lee *et al* 1986, 1993a, 1993b; Lin and Lee 1986, Lin *et al* 1988).

Petaurista philippensis occurs in geographic areas across Sri Lanka, India: north to Bombay and Rajasthan, S. Bihar, Burma, Thailand, S.China, including Hainan and Taiwan, and Indonesia (Agrawal and Chakraborty 1979, Wilson and Reeder 1993).

In India, the description (Blanford 1881, Wroughton 1911, Ellerman 1961), morphometrics (Xavier *et al* 1998), and the feeding and nesting habits (Rajamani 2000) of *P. philippensis* have been studied. Surveys in the early half of the century have recorded the occurrence of *P. philippensis* in various parts of India (Wroughton 1911, 1919; Hutton 1947, Menon 1962, 1964, 1965, Srinivasan 1977). Agarwal and Chakraborty (1979) catalogued the distribution of flying squirrel species in the Indian subregion from existing records. Recent studies have found the species to occur in large numbers in disturbed forest fragments and in plantations close to forested areas (Ashraf *et al* 1993, Umapathy and Kumar 2000a, Rajamani 2000). However, there is no documentation of the habitat requirements and the current distribution of *P. philippensis* across various forest types in the Western Ghats.

The species is known by the local name *paran* or *parachathan* in Malayalam and is called *mayapoonai* in Tamil.

Description of the species

Adapted from Ellerman (1961):

Colour: A greyish effect on the back, described by Blanford as 'grizzled brown, varying from deep chestnut to greyish brown in one direction and to sooty black in the other, the longer hairs partly white, giving a hoary appearance'. Parachute and forelimbs are usually brown. Feet mostly black. Tail black for the most part, but is sometimes greyish at the base. Underparts white, grey or drab grey, with never any red or rufous tinge apparent. Cheeks usually grey.

Table 2.1: Comparative summary of description of the two species.
(all measurements in cm.)

	<i>P. fuscocapillus</i>	<i>P. philippensis</i>
Head and body (max.) [□]	c.300	490
Tail (max.) [□]	c.250	550
Hind feet [□]	50-55	65-90
Skull: max. Length [□]	c.57	65-81
Maxillary tooth row [□]	11.1	15.0-17.8
Width of parachute near forelimb [□]	125	234
Width of parachute near hindlimb [□]	100	319
Dorsal pelage	Medium brown	Hoary, with white hair-tips
Cheeks	White, washed with yellow.	White or grey, never a rufous tinge
Feet	Pale yellowish brown	Feet black
Tail	Dusky brown, with a line of blackish hairs along the centre, and light brown on either sides.	Black, sometimes maybe grey at base.
Underside	Yellowish white extending to cheeks and under-lip	White or grey, never a rufous tinge.

[□] Corbett and Hill (1992).

[□] Xavier *et al* (1998).

(Pictures of study species on pages 36 and 37)

3. STUDY AREA

The study was carried out in the Western Ghats of Kerala and Tamil Nadu in South India. The Western Ghats is a 1400 km long chain of hills that runs parallel to the west coast of peninsular India from the river Tapti in the north to Kanyakumari in the south. Covering an area of 1,32,606 km sq., which is approximately 4.03% of the land area of India (Rodgers *et al* 2000), the Western Ghats extend over five states (Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Goa and Maharashtra) between 8°0' N to 12°30' N latitude and 75°0' E to 78°30' E longitude.

The hills rise up to an average elevation of 900-1500 m, sometimes rising up to heights of more than 2000 m. The southern western slopes receive an average of 2000-6000 mm of rainfall, and rainfall decreases from to the north and to the east (Nair 1991). The diversity of rainfall regimes and topography have resulted in a variety of vegetation types in the Western Ghats (for details refer to Champion and Seth 1968).

Forest types surveyed: Both Protected and Less Protected areas were surveyed during the study. Areas have been classified, as **Protected areas (PA)** when the levels of protection are high, and Wildlife Sanctuaries and National Parks, Tiger Reserve and Biosphere Reserves are included in this category. **Less Protected areas (LPA)** have been defined as areas with little or no protection, and where certain levels of extraction are permitted. Reserve Forests, plantations of the Forest Department, and private plantations and forests have been included in this category.

Vegetation types surveyed: The forest types recognised for this survey were **Evergreen forest, Moist Deciduous Forest, Dry Forests** (Dry Deciduous and Scrub), **Shola Forests**, and **Plantations** (comprising Coffee Plantations, Cardamom plantations, and Coconut Plantations). Sholas or high elevation montane Evergreen forests (Southern subtropical hill forest 8A/C1, Champion and Seth 1968) were considered distinct from Evergreen forests due to their distinct physiognomic features - stunted trees with less shapely boles covered with epiphytes. Sholas are usually confined to folds and depressions in the mountains and are characterised by medium (15-20 m) and small sized (7-15 m) trees (Lengerke and Blasco 1989 in Shankar and Sukumar 1999). These forest patches occur in a grassland Shola mosaic and are usually isolated form other patches of forest by grasslands.

A detailed list of km walked per altitude zone and per vegetation type with respect to the different sites is listed in Appendix 1.

Map 1: Study Area located in the Western Ghats, India.

Sites surveyed: The two southern most states were chosen for the survey as *P. f. fuscocapillus* is described as occurring in the state of Travancore, or present day Kerala, and most records of the species are from Kerala, with a few records from Tamil Nadu. While it is imperative that other areas in the Western Ghats be surveyed in order to obtain a complete picture of the distribution of the species, for the purpose of this study it was decided that it was necessary to verify previous records and judge the current distribution of the species in Kerala and Tamil Nadu. Forest sites were chosen all along the stretch of the Western Ghats in these two states, and sites chosen were representative of forest types in that region. Representative sites were sampled in all large tracts of forest, and few sites were sampled in all hill ranges of the Western Ghats of Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Table 3.1 (below) lists the areas surveyed with details of vegetation type sampled, and effort at each site. Numbered places correspond to numbers on Map 2. Sites are given one number, and different locations sampled within a site are not numbered due to the small size of the map (eg. Wynad WLS is numbered 30, and Muthanga and Kuppady, areas walked within this sanctuary are not numbered individually). However, if the site is large, then two numbers are used to indicate extent of site. (Eg. Kalakad-Mundanthurai TR has two sites marked).

Table 3.1: List of study areas, vegetation types surveyed and effort per area visited.
Numbered places correspond to numbers on Map 2.

No.	Name of Site	PA/ LPA	Vegetation type	Km. walked
1, 3	Kalakad-Mundanthurai Tiger Reserve	PA	EG, DF	16.6
2	Neyyar WLS	PA	MDF, DF	4.1
4	Peppara WLS	PA	EG, SF	4.9
5	Shendurny WLS	PA	MDF	5
6	Achankovil RF	LPA	EG	4
7	Ranni RF	LPA	EG	11.5
8	Periyar Tiger Reserve	PA	MDF	16.5
9	Idukki WLS	PA	EG	11
10	Munnar	LPA	CDP	8.4
11	Munnar – Kuttampuzha	LPA	EG	3.5
12	Thattekad BS	PA	MDF	2
13	Ernakulam	LPA	CCP	3
14	Pooyankutty	LPA	EG	0.6
15,16,17	Kodaikanal RF	LPA	SF	8.1
18	Chalakydy RF	LPA	EG, MDF, CCP, CFP.	11.4
19, 23, 24	Indira Gandhi WLS	PA	EG, MDF, CFP	32.5
21	Parambikulam WLS	PA	MDF	5.6
22	Dindigul RF	LPA	MDF	5
25	Silent Valley NP	PA	EG, CFP	17.3
26, 27	Nilgiris	PA	SF	3.8
28	Nilgiris –Gedde	PA	MDF	1
29	Nilgiris –Kothagiri	PA	SF	6.1
30	Wynad WLS	PA	MDF, DF	9.1
31	Kannavam RF	LPA	EG	1
32	Aralam WLS	PA	MDF	2
Not in map	Idukki KFDC plantations, close to Idukki WLS	LPA	CDP	2
	Mannarkad Private land	LPA	MDF	10

PA – Protected area; LPA – Less Protected area (defined on page 6).

WLS – Wildlife Sanctuary, NP – National Park, RF – Reserve Forest.

EG – Evergreen forest, MDF – Moist Deciduous Forest, SF– Shola Forest, DF – Dry Forest, CCP – Coconut plantation, CFP – Coffee Plantation, CDP – Cardamom Plantation

Map 2: Sites surveyed in the Western Ghats of Kerala and Tamil Nadu

4. METHODS

Forest and non-forest areas in the Western Ghats of Tamil Nadu and Kerala were sampled between January 2001 and May 2001.

4.1 Data Collection

Flying squirrel observations: Trails were walked at every study site primarily between 1900 and 0100 hrs though all hours of the night were sampled. Spotlighting was the primary method of locating flying squirrels. This method is widely used in the study of other nocturnal arboreal mammals (Lee *et al* 1993, Goldingay 1990) and has been established as effective in detecting arboreal mammals (Laurence and Laurence 1995). One modified torch fitted with a halogen bulb and connected to a 12V battery was used in addition to flashlights and headlights. All strata of the vegetation were scanned from different angles and squirrels were detected by eye-shine and then identified by the use of binoculars. Only confirmed sightings of the two species were used for analysis. Sightings when the animal moved away from the light too quickly or was too far away to be identified accurately were not taken into account. *P. philippensis* was also detected by their vocalisations, which are loud calls that are usually repeated monotonously (Prater 1971). The observer was familiar with the call (due to previous field experience with the species) and the call could be identified as being that of *P. philippensis* with accuracy. The call of *P. f. fuscocapillus* is not documented. Hutton (1949) in a description of the captive animal reports it to make growling noises, which he likens to a dog. One captive Small Travancore flying squirrel was observed in the zoo at Thattekad Bird Sanctuary, but the animal was not heard vocalising. The call is also not described as readily by locals as the call of *P. philippensis*. Calls of *P. f. fuscocapillus* were not used to locate the species. Nocturnal calls that were not the call of *P. philippensis* were not recorded.

For each squirrel sighted, the following characteristics were recorded: the species, time of the sighting, the height at which the animal was detected (estimated visually from the base of the tree in which it was detected), height of the tree, tree species, and the presence or absence of con-specifics. When possible; any observations of behaviour of the animal at the instant it was sighted were recorded. The age classes of the animals (adult, juvenile, sub-adult) were recorded whenever possible.

Habitat characteristics: The trees that the flying squirrels were sighted on were marked and a vegetation plot was laid around these trees during daytime to characterise parameters of the habitats used by flying squirrels. The distance to the four nearest trees from the tree where the animal was sighted were measured in order to enable some estimate of tree density. The girths and heights of all the five trees, including the one the squirrel was sighted on were also measured. In areas where no flying squirrels were encountered the same habitat parameters were recorded in random plots laid along the path walked in order to measure the parameters in the general habitat. Random plots were not laid within habitats where flying squirrels were sighted as the aim of collection of such habitat parameters was not to compare features of the habitat within a site, but to compare habitat characteristics across sites (to compare sites where flying squirrels were sighted with sites where they were not sighted). The perpendicular distance from the path to the sighting tree was noted. For every site/ walk, forest type, the altitude (with an altimeter) and location of the walk (with a GPS) were recorded.

Questionnaire: In addition to field surveys, a questionnaire (Appendix 3) was prepared to gather secondary information regarding the presence and awareness of the two species of flying squirrels at every site. Information on the natural history of the species was collected and an attempt was made to assess the threats to the two species. Information about other nocturnal mammals and arboreal herbivores was also collected whenever possible.

One week was spent at Karian Shola, an Evergreen forest in the Indira Gandhi WLS, Tamil Nadu, in order to make behavioural observations of the species, with particular emphasis on *P. f. fuscocapillus*. Karian Shola was chosen for such studies as both species have been reported at the site (Kannan 1993,

Ashraf, N.V.K. pers. comm). Night work was also logistically feasible at this site due to various reasons.

4.2 Data analysis

Encounter rate was calculated as the number of flying squirrels sighted per kilometer of walk. This was the unit of occurrence of flying squirrels that was used for analysis. The encounter rates of the two species of flying squirrels were assessed with respect to habitat types, elevation zones, habitat characteristics, and protected status of sampled areas. The statistical package SPSS (Norusis 1990) was used for most of the analysis.

When encounter rates of Protect areas and non protected areas were analyzed, the unit taken into account for the calculation of encounter rates was the encounter rate per trail in every site. site.

Mann Whitney U tests were used to analyze the encounter of flying squirrels with respect to habitat and elevation to determine –

- if the occurrence of flying squirrels varied across vegetation/ elevation categories, and
- if the occurrence of the two species of flying squirrels differed within a vegetation/ elevation category.

Three habitat characteristics that were thought to be important for flying squirrels were isolated for analysis: height, girth and a measure of density of the habitat. Distance from the tree the squirrels were sighted on to the nearest tree was used as a comparative (not absolute) measure of density of the stand. Mann Whitney U tests and Chi square tests were used to ascertain the effect of habitat parameters considered influence flying squirrel distribution and to determine -

- if habitat characteristics different in the habitats where flying squirrels occurred and where they did not.
- If habitat characteristics associated with the occurrence of the two species different from each other.

Mann Whitney U tests were used to test if the occurrence of flying squirrels in Protected areas differed from the occurrence of flying squirrels in the Less Protected areas surveyed.

5. DISTRIBUTION AND HABITAT PREFERENCES OF FLYING SQUIRRELS.

5.1 RESULTS

5.1.1 DISTRIBUTION OF FLYING SQUIRRELS

28 areas were surveyed in the Western Ghats of Tamil Nadu and Kerala, out of which 16 were protected areas and 12 were Less Protected areas. Protected Areas include Wildlife Sanctuaries, National parks, Tiger Reserves and one Biosphere Reserve. Less Protected areas include Reserve Forests and private land that is not under the control of the forest department.

Table 5.1: Encounter rates (Mean \pm S.D.) of the two species of flying squirrels in different sampling sites. Sites arranged from south to north.

Name of Site	n	<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>	<i>P. philippensis</i>
Kalakad-Mundanthurai TR	7	0	0.82 \pm 1.34
Neyyar WLS	2	0	0.66 \pm 0.94
Peppara WLS	2	0	0.15 \pm 0.22
Shendurny WLS	1	0.25	1.42
Achankovil RF	1	0.25	1
Ranni RF	2	0	0.68 \pm 0.44
Periyar TR	2	0	1.4 \pm 0.09
Idukki - KFDC plantation	1	0	0.5
Idukki WLS	1	0	0.63
Munnar	5	0	0.60 \pm 1.34
Munnar – Kuttampuzha	1	0.25	1
Thattakad BS	1	0.5	0
Ernakulam	1	0	0
Pooyankutty	1	0	6.66
Kodaikanal RF	5	0	2.03 \pm 2.46
Chalakyady RF	6	0	2.79 \pm 4.66
Indira Gandhi WLS	12	0.21 \pm 0.48	1.31 \pm 0.84
Parambikulam WLS	2	0	0.69 \pm 0.98
Dindigul RF	1	0	0.4
Mannarkad	2	0	0.14 \pm 0.20
Silent Valley NP	4	0	0.79 \pm 1.02
Nilgiris	3	0	0
Nilgiris –Gedde	1	0	2
Nilgiris –Kothagiri	3	0	2.08 \pm 2.26
Wynad WLS	3	0	2.20 \pm 3.20
Kannavam RF	1	0	0
Aralam WLS	1	0	0.5

NOTE: n is the number of different trails walked at a site. Trails repeated were pooled together as one trail. When S.D. is not available, it implies only one trail was sampled within an area. (Eg. only one trail (at Kattlipara) was sampled in Shendurny WLS, though it was walked more than once)

During the course of the survey, *P. philippensis* was encountered at 24 sites (85.71% of sites sampled) while *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered only in 5 sites (17.85 % of sites sampled) though these sites were widely spread across the southern Western Ghats (Refer Map 3).

Figure 5.1: Encounter rates of flying squirrels in Protected and Less Protected areas.

Encounter rates of both species of flying squirrels were higher in Less protected areas than in Protected areas. Encounter rates of *P. philippensis* (Less protected area: 1.51 squirrels/ km \pm 0.555 S.E., n=12 areas; Protected Areas: 0.90 squirrels/ km \pm 0.185 S.E., n=16 areas) also exhibited the same trend, while the encounter rate of *P. f. fuscocapillus* was marginally higher in Protected areas (0.06 squirrels/ km \pm 0.035 S.E., n=16 areas) than in Less Protected areas (0.04 squirrels/ km \pm 0.028 S.E., n=12 areas). Both *P. philippensis* and *P. f. fuscocapillus* did not differ significantly in their pattern of occurrence in Protected and Less protected areas (Mann Whitney U Test, *P. philippensis* : $p > 0.05$, *P. f. fuscocapillus*, $p > 0.05$).

The low encounter rate and infrequent sightings of *P. f. fuscocapillus* suggested that it occurs at lower densities than *P. philippensis* and information obtained locally regarding the presence of the species was also used to determine the possible distribution of the species.

P. philippensis was sighted in 4 of the sites where *P. f. fuscocapillus* was sighted, and though *P. philippensis* was not sighted at Thattekad BS during this survey, it is definitely known to occur at the site, as it was sighted on a previous visit to the sanctuary.

Except for dry forests, all habitat types were sampled in both Protected and Less Protected Areas (details of effort in Appendix 1). Dry forests were sampled only in Protected Areas, and there were no encounters of flying squirrels in dry forests. The encounter rate of *P. philippensis* was highest in Moist Deciduous forests in Pooyankutty, while the encounter rate of *P. f. fuscocapillus* was highest in Evergreen forest in Indira Gandhi WLS (Table 5.2).

During the course of the survey, elevations between 0 and 2200 m were sampled. With respect to altitude zones sampled, the encounter rate of *P. f. fuscocapillus* was highest at Thattekad Bird Sanctuary, in the zone 0-500m, while the encounter rate of *P. philippensis* was highest in Pooyankutty, also in the altitude zone 0-500m. Encounter rates of *P. philippensis* were also high in Kothagiri altitude 1500-2000m, and in Kodaikanal (2000-2500 m).

Table 5. 2: Encounter rates of the two species of flying squirrels in different vegetation types within each sampling site.

Name of Site	Evergreen			Moist Deciduous			Shola			Dry			Plantation		
	STFS	LBFS	S.D.	STFS	LBFS	S.D.	STFS	LBFS	S.D.	STFS	LBFS	S.D.	STFS	LBFS	S.D.
Kalakat-Mundanthurai TR	0 (5)	1.15 ± 1.49 (5)		-	-		-	-		0 (2)	-		-	-	
Neyyar WLS	-	-		0	1.33		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Peppara WLS	0	0.31		-	-		0	0		-	-		-	-	
Shendurmy WLS	-	-		0.25 ± 0.35 (2)	1.41 ± 0.11 (2)		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Achankovil RF	0.25	1		-	-		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Ranni RF	0 (3)	0.55 ± 0.37 (3)		-	-		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Periyar Tiger Reserve	0 (4)	1.43 ± 0.11 (4)		-	-		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Idukki - KFDC plantation	-	-		-	-		-	-		-	-		0	0.5	
Idukki WLS	0 (2)	0.63 ± 0.36 (2)		-	-		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Munnar	-	-		-	-		0	0		-	-		0	0	3
Munnar - Kuttampuzha	0.25 ± 0.35 (2)	1 ± 1.41 (2)		-	-		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Thattekad BS	-	-		0.5 ± 0.7 (2)	0 (2)		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Ernakulam	-	-		-	-		-	-		-	-		-	-	0
Pooyankutty	-	6.66		-	-		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Kodaikanal RF	-	-		-	-		0 (6)	2.69 ± 2.73 (6)		-	-		-	-	
Chalakudy RF	0 (2)	0.64 ± 0.02 (2)		0 (2)	6.08 ± 0.36 (2)		-	-		-	-		0 (2)	1.66 ± 2.35 (2)	
Indira Gandhi WLS	0.32 ± 0.57 (8)	1.30 ± 0.81 (8)		0 (3)	0.5 ± 0.86 (3)		-	-		-	-		0	1.66	
Parambikulam WLS	-	-		0 (2)	0.69 ± 0.98 (2)		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Dindigul RF	-	-		0	0.4		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Mannarkad	-	-		0 (2)	0.14 ± 0.2 (2)		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Silent Valley NP	0 (2)	0.35 ± 0.49 (2)		-	-		-	-		-	-		0	1.22 ± 1.44	
Nilgiris	-	-		-	-		0	0		-	-		-	-	
Nilgiris -Gedde	-	-		0	2		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Nilgiris -Kothagiri	-	-		-	-		0 (4)	3.12 ± 1.75 (4)		-	-		-	-	
Wynad WLS	-	-		0 (2)	3.31 ± 3.63 (2)		-	-		0	0		-	-	
Kannavam RF	0	0		-	-		-	-		-	-		-	-	
Aralam WLS	-	-		0	0.5		-	-		-	-		-	-	

STFS – small Travancore flying squirrel (*P.f.fuscicapillus*), LBFS – large brown flying squirrel (*P.philippensis*)
 NOTE: 'n' in brackets, is the number of walks per site. When S.D. is not available, it implies only one walk was surveyed within an area.

Table 5. 3: Encounter rates of the two species of flying squirrels in different altitude zones within each sampling site.

Name of Site	0-500 m		500 - 1000 m		1000 - 1500 m		1500 - 2000 m		2000 - 2500 m	
	STFS	LBFS	STFS	LBFS	STFS	LBFS	STFS	LBFS	STFS	LBFS
Kalakad-Mundanthurai TR	0	0	0 (3)	0.23±0.41 (3)	0 (3)	1.61 ±.81 (3)	-	-	-	-
Neyyar WLS	0	0	0	1.33	-	-	-	-	-	-
Peppara WLS	-	-	0	0.31	0	0	-	-	-	-
Shendurmy WLS	0.25 ± 0.35 (2)	1.41±1.11 (2)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Achankovil RF	0.25	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ranni RF	0 (3)	0.66 ± 0.47 (3)	0	0.4	-	-	-	-	-	-
Periyar Tiger Reserve	-	-	0 (4)	1.43±0.11 (4)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Idukki - KFDC plantation	-	-	0	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-
Idukki WLS	-	-	0 (2)	0.63±0.38 (2)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Munnar	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Munnar - Kuttampuzha	0.25 ± 0.35 (2)	1 ± 1.41 (2)	-	-	0	3	-	-	-	-
Thattekad BS	0.5 ± 0.7 (2)	0 (2)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ernakulam	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pooyankutty	0	6.66	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Kodaikanal RF	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Chalakudy RF	0 (3)	4.05 ± 6.88 (3)	0 (3)	1.54±1.55 (3)	-	-	0 (2)	2.08±0.58 (2)	0 (4)	3 ±3.46 (4)
Indira Gandhi WLS	0	0	0.37±0.60 (7)	1.41±0.90 (7)	0	1.01±0.64 (3)	0	0.66	-	-
Parambikulam WLS	0	0	0	1.38	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dindigul RF	-	-	0	0.4	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mannarkad	0 (2)	0.14 ± 0.2 (2)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Silent Valley NP	-	-	0 (4)	0.78±1.01 (4)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Nilgiris	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Nilgiris -Gedde	-	-	0	2	-	-	0	0	0	0
Nilgiris -Kothagiri	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wynad WLS	-	-	0 (3)	2.2 ± 3.2 (3)	-	-	0	3.12 ±.75 (4)	-	-
Kannavam RF	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Aralam WLS	0	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

STFS - small Travanvcore flying squirrel (*P.f.fuscocapillus*), LBFS - large brown flying squirrel (*P.philippensis*)
 NOTE: 'n' in brackets, is the number of walks per site. When S.D. is not available, it implies only one walk was surveyed within an area.

Map 3: Distribution of *P. f. fuscocapillus* in the Western Ghats of Kerala & Tamil Nadu

Map 4: Distribution of *P. philippensis* in the Western Ghats of Kerala & Tamil Nadu

5.1.2 HABITAT TYPES

5.1.2a Vegetation types and encounter rate

Flying squirrels were encountered in Evergreen forests, Moist Deciduous forests, Shola forests and in Plantations. *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered only in Evergreen forests and in Moist Deciduous forests. No flying squirrels were encountered in Dry forests. *P. philippensis* was encountered most in Moist Deciduous forests (1.60 squirrels/ km \pm 0.655 S.E., n=19 walks), followed by Plantations (1.36 squirrels/ km \pm 0.486 S.E., n=8 walks) and Evergreen forests (1.16 squirrels/ km \pm 0.286 S.E., n=25 walks).

Figure 5.2: Encounter rates of flying squirrels across different vegetation types.

n= number of walks

Occurrence of the two species of flying squirrels in each vegetation type.

The encounter rates per walk for both species of flying squirrels was compared within each vegetation category. The encounter rates of *P. f. fuscocapillus* in Evergreen forests (0.12 squirrels/ km \pm 0.069 S.E., n=25 walks) was significantly lower than the encounter rates of *P. philippensis* in Evergreen forests (1.16 squirrels/ km \pm 0.286 S.E., n= 25 walks) (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=n_2=25$, $z=-4.893$, $p < 0.001$). A similar pattern was seen in the occurrence of *P. f. fuscocapillus* (0.03 squirrels/ km \pm 0.028, n=19 walks) and *P. philippensis* (1.60 squirrels/ km \pm 0.655 S.E, n=19 walks), in Moist Deciduous Forest (Mann Whitney U Test, $n_1=n_2=19$, $z=-4.016$, $p < 0.0001$).

Occurrence of each species of flying squirrel across vegetation types.

The encounter rate of *P. f. fuscocapillus* in Moist Deciduous Forest was not significantly different from its encounter rate in Evergreen forest (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=19$, $n_2=25$, $z=-0.837$, $p > 0.05$). The encounter rate of *P. philippensis* in Evergreen forests was significantly different from its encounter rate in Shola forests (1.02 squirrels/ km \pm 0.463 S.E., n=16 walks) (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=25$, $n_2=16$, $z=-2.006$, $p > 0.05$).

Examining occurrence of the two species across different vegetation types, it was seen that *P. f. fuscocapillus* was specific to two vegetation types, Evergreen and Moist Deciduous forest while *P. philippensis* was more widely distributed across vegetation types. *P. philippensis* was encountered more than that of *P. f. fuscocapillus* in both habitat types where the species occurred together. The encounter rate of *P. f. fuscocapillus* was not significantly different in Moist Deciduous Forests and in Evergreen forests, though the encounter rate in Evergreen forests was higher than the encounter rate in Moist deciduous forests. The encounter rate of *P. philippensis* was significantly different only between Evergreen forests and Sholas, and the encounter rate was higher in Evergreen forests. *P. philippensis* was encountered more in Moist Deciduous forests than in any other vegetation type.

5.1.2b Altitude and encounter rate

P. f. fuscocapillus was not encountered above 900 m. *P. philippensis* was encountered up to a maximum elevation of 2050 m. Encounter rates of both species of flying squirrels taken together was highest in the altitude class 0-500 m (1.40 squirrels/ km \pm 0.724 S.E., n=18 walks). *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered more in the elevation class 0-500 m. (0.69 squirrels/ km \pm 0.058 S.E., n=19 walks) than between 500-1000m (0.08 squirrels/ km \pm 0.033 S.E., n=30 walks). The encounter rate of *P. philippensis* is highest at 0-500 m (1.33 squirrels/ km \pm 0.726 S.E., n=18 walks), followed by 1000-1500m (1.23 squirrels/ km \pm 0.446 S.E., n=9 walks) and 1500-2000 m (1.20 squirrels/ km \pm 0.229 S.E., n=30 walks). *P. philippensis* was sighted more than *P. f. fuscocapillus* at all elevation levels (Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.3: Encounter rates (Mean \pm S.E.) of flying squirrels across different altitudes.

n=number of walks

Occurrence of the two species of flying squirrels within each elevation zone.

The encounter rates of the two species were compared within each elevation class. The encounter rate of *P. philippensis* (1.33 squirrels/ km \pm 0.726 S.E., n=18 walks) was significantly greater than the encounter rate of *P. f. fuscocapillus* (0.69 squirrels/ km \pm 0.058 S.E., n=18 walks) in the elevation range 0-500 m (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=n_2=18$, $z=1.605$, $p<0.05$). The mean encounter rate of the two species (*P. philippensis*: 1.20 squirrels/ km \pm 0.229 S.E., n=30 walks; *P. f. fuscocapillus*: 0.08 squirrels/ km \pm 0.058 S.E., n=30 walks) of flying squirrels was not found to be different in the class intervals 500-1000 m (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=n_2=30$, $z=1.086$, $p>0.05$). The pattern of occurrence of the encounter rates of the two species in this elevation class was different (Kolmogorov Smirnov two sample test, $n_1=n_2=30$, $z=2.783$, $p<0.001$). While *P. philippensis* occurs more evenly across habitat types, the occurrence of *P. f. fuscocapillus* in only certain vegetation types within this elevation class probably accounts for the difference in the distribution pattern of the two species.

Occurrence of each species of flying squirrels across elevations.

The encounter rate of *P. f. fuscocapillus* did not differ significantly between any two elevation zones. *P. philippensis* occurred more in the elevation zone 0-500 m than it did between 500 and 1000 m (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=18$, $n_2=30$, $z=-2.060$, $p<0.05$). The encounter rates of *P. philippensis* in the elevation range 0-500m was also significantly greater than the encounter rate in the elevation range 2000-2500 m (1.204 squirrels/ km \pm 0.109 S.E., n=6 walks) (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=18$, $n_2=6$, $z=-2.038$, $p<0.05$).

Summarising encounter of flying squirrels across elevations; it was seen that *P. f. fuscocapillus* was not encountered above 900 m while *P. philippensis* was encountered over a wide range of altitudes ranging from 50 m – 2050 m. Both species were encountered most in the altitude range 0-500 m. The occurrence of the two species was different in the altitude class 0-500m, and *P. philippensis* was encountered more than *P. f. fuscocapillus*. *P. f. fuscocapillus* did not occur differently across different

altitudes. The encounter rate of *P. philippensis* was lowest in the altitude range 2000-2500 m and this was significantly different from the encounter of the species in the altitude range 0-500m.

5.1.3 FOREST STRUCTURE: CHARACTERISTICS AND USE BY FLYING SQUIRRELS.

5.1.3a Tree Height

Characteristics of stands

The mean height of trees on which *P. philippensis* was sighted (22.59 m \pm 0.62 S.E., n= 93 trees) was not significantly greater than the mean height of trees on which *P. f. fuscocapillus* was sighted (22.35 m \pm 1.37 S.E., n=14 trees) (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=92$, $n_2=14$, $z=-0.89$, $p=0.929$).

Fig 5.4: Height of trees in plots where flying squirrels were and were not sighted.

Fig 5.5: Girth of trees in plots where flying squirrels were and were not sighted.

The heights of trees in random plots (where no flying squirrels were sighted) (14.38 m \pm 0.35 S.E., n=207 trees) was significantly lower than the heights of trees where *P. philippensis* (16.49 m \pm 0.32 S.E., n=474 trees) was sighted (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1= 474$, $n_2= 207$, $z=-3.50$, $p=0.000$). The heights of trees where *P. f. fuscocapillus* (17.79 m \pm 0.70 S.E., n=70 trees) was sighted and in random plots (where no squirrels were sighted) were not significantly different (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1= 207$, $n_2= 35$, $z=-4.12$, $p>0.05$). The height of trees in the plots where *P. f. fuscocapillus* was sighted was not significantly different (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1= 474$, $n_2= 70$, $z=-1.919$, $p=0.055$) from the heights of trees in the plots where *P. philippensis* was sighted though the height of trees in the *P. f. fuscocapillus* plots was greater than the height of trees in the *P. philippensis* plots.

The height of the tree utilised by the flying squirrels was compared with the height of the other trees in the plot. The height of the tree utilised by *P. f. fuscocapillus* (22.36 m \pm 1.38 S.E., n=14 trees) was significantly higher than the height of other trees in the plot (16.65 m \pm 0.74 S.E., n=56 trees) (Mann Whitney U Test, $n_1= 56$, $n_2= 14$, $z = -3.25$, $p<0.001$). The height of trees utilised by *P. philippensis* was also significantly higher (22.59 m \pm 0.63 S.E., n=93 trees) than the height of other trees in the plot (14.88 m \pm 0.37 S.E., n=264 trees) (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1= 264$, $n_2= 93$, $z = -9.16$, $p< 0.001$).

Height utilisation by flying squirrels

The height occupied by the two flying squirrels differed significantly (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1= 18$, $n_2= 126$, $z=2.152$, $p=0.036$) and *P. philippensis* was encountered higher (18.86 m \pm 0.516 S.E, n=126) on the tree than *P. f. fuscocapillus* (18.27 m \pm 1.096 S.E, n=18). Regression analysis was used to determine if the height occupied by the animals increased with the height of the tree. The height occupied by *P. philippensis* was linearly regressed against tree height, and it was seen that the height occupied by the animal increased with tree height ($r^2 =0.621$, $f= 206.69$, $p<0.001$) (Fig. 5.6). Three outliers were removed, these being heights at which the squirrels landed after a glide, which is not the usual height occupied by *P. philippensis*. As soon as an animal lands after a glide, it immediately moves up the tree, and does not utilise the lower strata of the tree for any other activities. *P. f. fuscocapillus* did not occupy heights in a linear relation to the height of the tree, i.e., the height

occupied by *P. f. fuscocapillus* did not increase with tree height. When a quadratic regression was performed, it was seen that *P. f. fuscocapillus* occupied increasing heights as the height of the tree increased, but the height utilised decreased as the trees were of height greater than 35m. ($r^2= 0.621$, $f=206$. $p>0.05$, $n=14$) (Fig. 5.7). Trends of height were unclear for this species, and more intensive studies are called for in order to understand use of vertical strata.

Figure 5.6: Regressing height occupied by *P. philippensis* against height of the tree.

Figure 5.7: Regressing height occupied by *P. f. fuscocapillus* against height of the tree.

Though there was considerable overlap of tree strata utilised by the two species, *P. f. fuscocapillus* was sighted more often in the lower strata (5-15 m) while *P. philippensis* was sighted more often in the higher strata (15-30 m) (Figure 5.8). *P. f. fuscocapillus* was also not sighted as high in the canopy as *P. philippensis*. Neither flying squirrel was observed below a height of 5 m.

Figure 5.8: Tree strata utilised by flying squirrels

Analysis of tree height in relation to flying squirrel occurrence revealed that tree height was an important characteristic in the choice of habitat by flying squirrels. Stands were shorter in habitats where no flying squirrels were encountered than where flying squirrels were encountered. This held true for the two individual species as well. Stands where *P. f. fuscocapillus* occurred were taller than stands where they did not, and stands where *P. philippensis* occurred were taller than the stands that they did not occur in. However, stands occupied by the two species did not differ significantly in height from each other. Height of the trees occupied by flying squirrels within a stand also seemed to be important. Both species were found on trees that were taller than the surrounding trees in the plot, suggesting a selective choice towards utilisation of taller trees in a habitat. Comparison of utilisation

of forest strata by the two species revealed that *P. philippensis* occupied significantly higher heights than did *P. f. fuscocapillus*. Both species were seen to utilise tree strata in proportion to the height of the tree.

5.1.3b Tree Girth

General characteristics of stands

The girths of trees in plots where no flying squirrels were sighted ($1.07 \text{ m} \pm 0.06 \text{ S.E.}$, $n=225$ trees) was significantly lower than the girths of trees where *P. philippensis* was sighted ($1.50 \text{ m} \pm 0.06 \text{ S.E.}$, $n=475$ trees) (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=475$, $n_2=225$, $z=-5.54$, $p<0.001$) (Figure 5.5). The girths of trees in random plots was significantly lower than the mean girth in plots where *P. f. fuscocapillus* ($1.27 \text{ m} \pm 0.10 \text{ S.E.}$, $n=70$) was sighted. (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=70$, $n_2=225$, $z=-2.14$, $p<0.05$) (Figure 5.5).

Figure 5.9: Girth wise distribution of trees in plots.

The distribution of girths in plots where no flying squirrels were sighted was significantly different from the distribution of girths where flying squirrels were sighted ($\chi^2 = 43.43$, $df=6$, $p<0.001$). The distribution of trees in plots where *P. f. fuscocapillus* was sighted was significantly different from the plots where no flying squirrels were sighted ($\chi^2 = 13.73$, $df=3$, $p<0.01$), and a similar pattern was seen between plots where *P. philippensis* was sighted and where no flying squirrels were sighted ($\chi^2 = 42.62$, $df=3$, $p<0.001$). However, the distribution of the girth classes of trees in *P. f. fuscocapillus* plots and in *P. philippensis* plots were not different ($\chi^2 = 1.01$, $df=3$, $p>0.05$). Plots where no flying squirrels were sighted were dominated by trees in the lower girth classes (0-1 m). Plots where flying squirrels were sighted had relatively more trees in the higher girth classes (Figure 5.9).

Girth of trees utilised by flying squirrels

The mean girth of trees on which *P. philippensis* was sighted was 2.42 m ($\pm 0.20 \text{ S.E.}$, $n= 96$ trees) and the mean girth of the trees on which *P. f. fuscocapillus* was sighted was 1.93 m ($\pm 0.24 \text{ S.E.}$, $n=14$ trees). The girth of trees on which *P. philippensis* was sighted was not significantly different from the girth of trees on which *P. f. fuscocapillus* was sighted. (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=96$, $n_2=14$, $z=-0.78$, $p>0.05$).

The girth of trees utilised by the flying squirrels was compared with the girths of the other trees in the plot. The girths of trees utilised by *P. f. fuscocapillus* ($1.93 \text{ m} \pm 0.24 \text{ S.E.}$, $n=14$ trees) were significantly higher than the girths of other trees in the plot ($1.10 \text{ m} \pm 0.10 \text{ S.E.}$, $n=56$ trees) (Mann Whitney U Test, $n_1=56$, $n_2=14$, $z= -3.39$, $p<0.01$). The girth of trees utilised by *P. philippensis* was also significantly greater ($2.45 \text{ m} \pm 0.22 \text{ S.E.}$, $n=102$ trees) than the average girth of trees in the plot ($1.37 \text{ m} \pm 0.10$, $n=406$ trees) (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1=406$, $n_2=10$, $z =-9.40$, $p<0.01$).

Tree girth and tree heights in the vegetation plots for the two species were seen to be correlated at high levels of significance. Tree girth and height were correlated in the vegetation plots around flying

squirrel sighting trees (*P. philippensis*: Kendall's $\tau = 0.53$, $p < 0.001$, $n=471$; *P. f. fuscocapillus*: Kendall's $\tau = 0.481$, $p < 0.001$, $n=70$).

Girth and height were not significantly correlated for trees where *P. f. fuscocapillus* was sighted (Kendall's $\tau = 0.011$, $p > 0.05$, $n=14$), though they were significantly correlated for trees where *P. philippensis* was sighted (Kendall's $\tau = 0.34$, $p < 0.001$, $n=92$). The height of the trees utilised by *P. philippensis* was also regressed with the girth of trees, and height increased with girth.

Summarising the analysis of tree girths and flying squirrel occurrence, it was seen that tree girth was another habitat characteristic that probably influenced the choice of stands by flying squirrels. Tree girth was significantly different higher in stands where flying squirrels were encountered than where flying squirrels were not encountered. As was seen with height, it was seen that each species of flying squirrel occurred in stands where the girth of trees was significantly greater than the girth in stands where they did not occur. Flying squirrels also preferred to use trees of larger girth with a stand. This was seen to hold good for both species of flying squirrels and they selectively utilised trees of larger girth. The height and girth of trees utilised by *P. philippensis* was significantly positively correlated, whereas the height and girth of trees utilised by *P. f. fuscocapillus* was not significantly correlated, though this could be an artefact of low sample size. Tree girth and tree height for the general population were also significantly correlated.

5.1.3c Distance to the nearest neighbour (a measure of density)

Distance to the nearest neighbour was used as a measure of closeness or density of trees. The mean distance from the tree where *P. philippensis* was sighted to the nearest neighbour was 3.06 m (± 0.23 S.E., $n=97$) and the distance from the tree *P. f. fuscocapillus* was sighted on to the nearest neighbour was 2.59 m (± 0.61 S.E., $n=14$).

The distance to the nearest tree in the *P. philippensis* tree plots was not significantly different from the distance to the nearest tree in the *P. f. fuscocapillus* tree plots (Mann Whitney U Test, $n_1=14$, $n_2=97$, $z=-0.75$, $p > 0.05$). The distance to the nearest tree in random plots in habitats where no flying squirrels were encountered was 2.07 m (± 0.18 S.E., $n=45$) was lower than where flying squirrels were encountered. The distance to the nearest tree was not significantly different between the *P. f. fuscocapillus* plots and random tree plots (Mann Whitney U tests, $n_1=45$, $n_2=14$, $z = -0.36$, $p > 0.05$), though the distance to nearest tree was higher in *P. f. fuscocapillus* plots than in the random plots. The distance to the nearest neighbour in *P. philippensis* plots was significantly greater than the random plots (Mann Whitney U test, $n_1 = 45$, $n_2=97$, $z = -1.96$, $p < 0.05$).

The third habitat characteristic that seemed to influence choice of utilisation of habitat by flying squirrels was the distance between trees, which was used as a rough estimate of density of the stand. The distance to the nearest tree was not significantly different in stands where *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered and where no flying squirrels were encountered. However *P. philippensis* seemed to prefer stands that were less dense, and stands where *P. philippensis* was encountered had significantly lower tree densities than stands where they were not encountered.

5.2 DISCUSSION

Flying squirrels were encountered in a variety of habitats during the survey. The distribution of the two species overlapped across both habitats and altitudes. There was no discernible trend in the occurrence of either species of flying squirrel with respect to elevation. While *P. f. fuscocapillus* was not sighted above 900 m, *P. philippensis* was encountered at higher elevations, though the encounter rate of the species decreased with an increase in altitude.

P. philippensis was sighted only in a few of the high elevation montane forests (Sholas) sampled. With increasing human activities, forest areas and grasslands around Sholas have been converted to Tea, Pine (*Pinus patula*), Wattle (*Acacia mearnsii*), Coffee (*Coffea* sp.), Cardamom, and Eucalyptus plantations (*Eucalyptus* sp.). Remnant forest patches sometimes abut towns and plantations and at

certain sites, though the forest patch was termed a "Shola" (described in Chapter 3), it was unclear if these were originally surrounded by grasslands or if they were remnant tracts of forest that were once contiguous with lower elevation forests. The species was encountered in Shola patches such as described above in the Palni Hills (Kodaikanal) and in the Nilgiris, where extensive Wattle and Eucalyptus plantations have altered the natural ecosystem.

Isolation of Shola forests is one factor that might be responsible for the absence of flying squirrels. Flying squirrels were not sighted in isolated Shola patches though other arboreal mammals like Giant squirrels (*Ratufa indica*) and Nilgiri Langurs (*Trachypithecus johnii*) were seen to occur in these forests (personal observation). Giant squirrels are known to cross open spaces to reach nearby forest patches (Datta and Goyal 1996, S.D.Ripley in Moore 1952) and probably travel between Sholas. It is not known if *P. philippensis* or *P. f. fuscocapillus* cross open spaces by travelling on the ground. Another factor responsible for the absence of flying squirrels in most Shola forests might be the height of the forest. Sholas are stunted forests (Champion and Seth 1968), and this might deter flying squirrels from colonising these areas, as height of the forest might be a habitat parameter important to flying squirrels (discussed in greater detail further). The Sholas where the squirrels were sighted (Bombay Shola, Kookal Shola, and Longwood Shola) were not stunted forests, and were different in physiognomy from Sholas where flying squirrels were not sighted.

P. philippensis was also encountered in Plantations. In Cardamom Plantations and sometimes in Coffee Plantations, the overstorey of the forest is retained as shade and only the middle story and the understorey are removed. When the overstorey is not logged, the niche occupied by flying squirrels is not destroyed as large food trees and large trees with hollows that serve as nest sites are retained. This probably explains the occurrence of flying squirrels in plantations. Flying squirrels have been reported to occur in other plantations (coconut, cashew) and are reported to be pests to the coconut crop.

Arboreal mammals are strongly influenced by the structure and composition of forest vegetation (Lemos de Sa and Strier 1992). The results of this survey indicated that flying squirrels have strong preferences for certain habitat attributes, and this probably has a greater influence on their presence or absence at a site than vegetation type or altitude.

Flying squirrels showed a preference for stands with trees of greater girth and height. Stands where the species did not occur were short and the mean girth of trees was lower. The two species also selectively chose trees that were taller and larger in girth than the surrounding trees in the stands that they occurred in. The preference for tall large trees might be influenced by their feeding and nesting habits or by their mode of locomotion.

Flying squirrels, particularly of the genus *Petaurista*, are largely folivorous. Consumption of young leaves is known to be more nutritious than consumption of older leaves, which are tougher and more fibrous (Coley 1983). Kawamichi (1997) reported that *P leucogynys* preferred young leaves, and their consumption of mature leaves was used as an index of negative food availability. Tall rain forest trees tend to produce many new leaves simultaneously, while smaller trees and lianas produce only a few new leaves at a time (Payne 1979). Tree girth is also often an indicator of tree maturity and reflects the tree's ability to produce fruit (Leighton and Leighton 1982). By concentrating on large food sources such as tall trees, animals can spend less time and energy searching for and travelling between other food sources. Gliders (*Petaurus australis*) in Australia were seen to feed extensively on the flowers of trees of large DBH, which was positively correlated with the number of flowers on the tree (Goldingay 1990). Giant squirrels (*Ratufa indica*) have also been seen to feed on trees of larger girth (Datta and Goyal 1996, Mali 1998).

The presence of flying squirrels in stands with larger trees might also be due to the greater availability of nest cavities in such stands. *P. philippensis* was seen to selectively utilise larger trees for nesting purposes (Rajamani 2000). Other hollow nesting vertebrates such as hornbills have been observed to utilise large trees for nesting (Poonswad 1995, Mudappa and Kannan 1996). Poonswad (1995) has reasoned that this selective usage might be due to the availability of suitable cavities only in such trees. Certain large trees are also more durable and long-lived than other trees in the forest, and have a higher probability of accumulating cavities.

Gliding is thought to have evolved in order to facilitate travel between tall emergents in the Dipterocarp forests, both in order to reduce the possibility of predation, and to enable species to exploit food resources more efficiently (Emmons 1995). Longer glides are more energy efficient and increase the amount of food resources that can be exploited. Increasing the height from which a glide is begun increases the distance that can be covered, and gliding in taller stands might be more beneficial to animals as they can access more food resources with low energy expenditure. Various species of flying squirrels have been observed to utilise large trees for gliding (*Glaucomys volans*: Bendel and Gates 1987, *Petaurista leucogynys*: Ando and Shiraishi in Bendel and Gates 1987). Barrett saw a similar trend for *Petaurista petaurista*, but reasoned that the use of higher strata of the forest by flying squirrels was not a function of the need for a higher launching point for glides but was related to the greater availability of more stable strata higher in the canopy.

P. philippensis was found in less dense vegetation than was *P. f. fuscocapillus*. Vegetation where *P. philippensis* occurred was also less dense than vegetation where no flying squirrels were seen. Thorington and Heaney (1981) have hypothesised that larger flying squirrels, with a heavier wing loading, are better adapted to gliding in more open forest area where manoeuvrability is less of a problem. In contrast, smaller flying squirrels are better adapted to gliding in more dense areas where wind turbulence is lower and where slow flight speed and higher manoeuvrability are important. Reports and studies of *P. philippensis* and *P. f. fuscocapillus* also indicate that the large flying squirrel was more common in more open areas, while the smaller flying squirrel was usually confined to denser forest stands. Menon (1962, 1964, 1965) reports that *P. philippensis* was common and occurred frequently in plantations across various districts in Kerala while *P. f. fuscocapillus* was confined to dense forests. *P. philippensis* was encountered more at the forest edge than in the forest interior in a forest fragment in South India, and tree densities were considerably lower at the edge than in the interior (Rajamani 2000). A species of small flying squirrel in the temperate regions, *Glaucomys sabrinus* (the northern flying squirrel), occurred at low densities in partially clear-cut stands and was found to increase in density with an increase in stand age (Rosenberg *et al* 1996, Carey *et al* 1992, Witt 1992).

Applying the habitat preferences observed to the different vegetation types surveyed, it could be hypothesised that habitat features determine the distribution of flying squirrels. Examining height of forests, it is known that Evergreen forests contain the tallest trees (25-30 m tall), and trees in Moist Deciduous forests are also moderately tall (10-20 m). Dry forests typically contain trees 10-15 m in height (Utkarsh *et al* 1998). Most sightings of flying squirrels were concentrated in the tree strata between 15-30m, and there were only a few observations of utilisation of the tree strata between 0-15 m. Flying squirrels were not encountered in Dry forests and were encountered most in Evergreen and Moist Deciduous forests (and in plantations where the shade trees are the overstorey of Evergreen forests), and it is possible that the height of the forests and the height utilised by flying squirrels affects this distribution. Shola Forests are typically described as short (10-15m) (Utkarsh *et al* 1998). However, as has been explained earlier, the Shola forests where squirrels were sighted were tall (Kodaikanal, Kothagiri), and no squirrels were sighted in stunted isolated Shola patches (Peppara WLS, Nilgiris).

The Small Travancore flying squirrel was seen to occur sympatrically with the Large Brown flying squirrel in all the habitats where it was encountered. Related species sharing finite resources can coexist in a habitat by partitioning resources and by occupying different niches within this habitat. Niche separation between syntopic species can occur in a number of ways. Species can differ in the habitat preferred, in patterns of utilisation of habitat structure, or by differences in diet. Flying squirrel species were seen to have distinct patterns of utilisation of the vertical vegetation structure. The Large Brown flying squirrel predominantly utilised the higher strata of the canopy, while the Small Travancore flying squirrel primarily utilised the lower strata of the forest. Other sympatric flying squirrel species have also been seen to occupy different heights (Lee *et al* 1986). Different vertical strata make up separate micro niches and have been shown to be important in niche separation for tropical rain forest squirrels in Africa (Emmons 1980) and in South east Asia (Payne 1979, Whitten 1981). Sympatric Lorises and Galagines were seen to utilise different strata and structural supports, according to their sizes and modes of locomotion (Charles-Dominique 1972).

Differences in body size and food requirements allow closely related species to coexist in the same habitats (Brown and Bowers 1984). *P. philippensis* and *P. f. fuscocapillus* differ both in body size (for details refer Table 2.1) and in their food habits. *P. philippensis* is a large flying squirrel with a head and body length of 490 mm while *P. f. fuscocapillus* is a medium sized flying squirrel measuring c.300 mm (Corbett and Hill 1992). Muul and Lim (1978) have classified the two species according to size and degree of folivory. The smallest species of flying squirrels were seen to be less herbivorous while the largest species were the most herbivorous. *Petaurista* is described as the most folivorous genus of flying squirrels, and *P. philippensis* falls within the herbivore Class 4 (herbivore classes defined by Eisenberg 1978). The diet of species in this class is dominated (> 40%) by leaves. *P. philippensis* was seen to consume largely leaves and fruits in a forest fragment in the Western Ghats (Rajamani 2000). *Petinomys fuscocapillus* is classified as belonging to the herbivore Class 3 with a diet consisting of buds, blossoms, leaves, and young shoots (from 30-40%). Examination of stomach contents of *P. f. fuscocapillus* revealed that most of the mass consumed was leaves, buds, seeds and seed coats, fruit pulp, barks, and part of an insect (Xavier *et al* 1996). 50% of the stomach content consisted of fruit pulp while 35% comprised of fruits and leaves. However, there is no information available on the ecology of two species in the same habitat in the wild, and how they partition food resources and space. Detailed studies of the two species are required before niche separation and habitat utilisation by the species can be completely understood.

6. BEHAVIOUR

6.1 RESULTS

Flying squirrels were encountered on 210 occasions during the survey. *P. philippensis* was encountered on 199 occasions and *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered on 11 occasions.

Whenever possible, behaviour was recorded at the instant the animal was sighted, and this was used to construct activity patterns of the species (Fig 6.1). On 31 occasions (19.75% of the observations), individuals reacted to the presence of the observer, either by moving or gliding out of sight. Several individuals began to vocalise and this is thought to a reaction to the light shone by the observer.

Figure 6.1: Percentage frequency of observed flying squirrel activities at first observation.

Flying squirrels were observed feeding on 35 occasions. On 29 occasions, the part consumed was recorded. *P. philippensis* was observed feeding on leaves (16 occasions), fruits (6 occasions) and flowers (6 occasions). Both tender leaves and mature leaves were consumed, fruits consumed were both ripe and unripe fruits. On five occasions con-specifics were observed on the same tree as the animal that was feeding. *P. f. fuscocapillus* was observed feeding on 3 occasions, and was feeding on leaves on all three occasions. On one occasion it was also feeding on fruits. *P. f. fuscocapillus* was sensitive to light, and on most occasions either moved away from the light or sat immobile for as long as the light was shone on it.

P. philippensis was also observed foraging on 12 occasions. These are defined as occasions when animals were seen searching or handling food, but were not seen consuming any food items. *P. philippensis* were observed feeding and foraging at an average height of 19.31m (± 0.81 S.E., n=41). On 5 occasions, con-specifics were seen on the same tree as the animal that was feeding.

Only on two occasions did animals stop feeding and glide away, presumably, as they were disturbed, but on all other occasions' animals did not stop feeding.

P. philippensis was located by its vocalisations on 53 occasions. The animal has a distinctive call that carries over some distance and it was not possible to locate all animals that were heard calling. When animals that were vocalising were located, they were at an average height of 20.5 m (± 2.44 S.E., n=7). On three occasions, more than one individual was on the tree, and on three occasions animals were observed to respond to the calls of others. On two occasions, the animals that responded to calls and moved towards the calling animals were infants.

On 32 occasions the animal sighted was motionless sitting on a branch and it is not clear if this was a reaction to the presence of the observer.

Activity patterns

Trails were walked during all hours of the night, and most encounters were recorded between 2030 hrs and 2330 hrs.

Figure 6.2: Number of flying squirrels sighted over time.

Figure 6.3: Activity patterns of flying squirrels. (The frequency of activities occurring over time has been plotted to construct an activity pattern.)

Flying squirrels begin feeding around 1830 hrs (Fig 6.3). While both feeding and calling begin around 1900 hrs, the animals were seen to call much more than feed between 1900 hrs and 2030 hrs. The most number of calling individuals was seen at 2030 hrs. As the number of individuals seen calling reduces, the number of individuals seen feeding increases, and then drops around 2200 hrs. At 2200 hrs most individuals were noticed either calling or sitting. A second peak in calling activity was noted at 2200 hrs, though this peak was less than the first one. Again at 2230, as the number of individuals seen calling reduces, the number of individuals seen feeding increases. The number of individuals seen sitting reaches a peak at 2230 hrs. Animals were seen resting (lying flat on the branch of a tree) only after 2300 hrs.

Roost sites of *P. f. fuscicapillus*

Two roost sites of *P. f. fuscicapillus* were located during the survey. One roost site was located in Thattekad Bird Sanctuary, and the roost was located as the animal was spotted exiting the cavity. The nest was located on a Teak (*Tectona grandis*) tree that was located close to the bank of the Periyar in degraded Moist Deciduous forest. The other observation was during the daytime, when *P. f. fuscicapillus* was flushed out of its hollow in Moist Deciduous forest at Achankovil RF. The animal

exited the nest and immediately glided to a tree about 60m away, moved up the trunk and went into a hollow. This implies that it was probably familiar with its surroundings.

Table 6.1: Description of hollows of *P. f. fuscocapillus*

	Roost 1	Roost 2	Roost 3
Site	Thattekad BS	Achankovil RF	Achankovil RF
Habitat type	Teak+Moist Deciduous	Moist Deciduous	Moist Deciduous
Tree Species	<i>Tectona grandis</i>	?	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i>
Height of hollow (m)	10	17	15
Height of tree (m)	20	30	27
Shape of hollow	Round	Longitudinal	Round

Occurrence of animals in social groups.

Out of the sightings of *P. philippensis* where the age class of the animal could be identified with confidence (n=89), 48.31% were adults, 26.99% were juveniles and 20.22% were infants. Animals were sighted alone or with con-specifics. A chi square test for two independent samples revealed that adults were more likely to be found alone ($\chi^2 = 4.19$, $df=1$, $p<0.05$), as was the case with juveniles ($\chi^2 = 7.142$, $df =1$, $p<0.01$). Infants of *P. philippensis* however would either be found alone or with con-specifics ($\chi^2 = 0$, $df =1$, $p>0.05$).

Size and age classes were not determined for *P. f. fuscocapillus*. On one occasion two individuals, possible an adult and a juvenile, were seen 11 m away from each other on neighbouring trees. All other sightings of *P. f. fuscocapillus* were of solitary individuals.

6.2 DISCUSSION

P. f. fuscocapillus and *P. philippensis* are hypothesised to differ in their food habits, with *P. philippensis* being the more folivorous of the two. *P. philippensis* was observed feeding on leaves more than on other plant parts, though it was observed feeding on flowers and fruits. On two occasions *P. philippensis* was observed feeding on the fruit of *Mangifera* sp. It consumed the peel and the pulp of the fruit, but the seed was not consumed and was dropped. On other occasions *P. philippensis* was seen to consume the fruits of *Ficus* sp. On other occasions, *P. philippensis* was observed reaching out and dragging and plucking branches of *Anogeissus* sp. towards itself. It was observed consuming the leaves whole, leaving behind only the petiole. Muul and Lim (1978) hypothesise that the long fingers and strong grasp of flying squirrels of the genus *Petaurista* is an adaptation for a folivorous mode of life. The ability to pull branches towards itself enables it to forage more easily.

P. f. fuscocapillus is said to feed on fruits, flowers, seeds, leaves and insects. *P. f. fuscocapillus* was seen plucking a small twig that had young leaves on it, and it consumed the leaves from the base of the stem. It then held the twig in its mouth and moved up the tree, where it sat holding the twig and feeding on the leaves. This species was found to be quite shy of light, and often would freeze or try to move away when light was shone on it, making observations of behaviour difficult. *P. philippensis* was often observed on trees with many clumps of fern on the trunk and branches. On several occasions *P. f. fuscocapillus* was observed sitting in fern clumps, and it is possible that the species foraged for insects in such clumps.

The average height of the roosts of *P. f. fuscocapillus* was 14m (n=3). Studies have recorded the nest of other species of *Petinomys* at a height of 3- 4 m (Payne *et al* 1985). Nests were not located at such low heights in this study. Nests of *P. philippensis* were located at a slightly higher average height of 18m on rainforest trees in the Anamalai hills, and the species was seen to selectively choose tall trees for nesting (Rajamani 2000). It is not known if there is any niche separation between the two species in terms of cavities occupied. Detailed documentation of roosting habits will provide insight into competition for cavities and cavity requirements.

Eisenberg (1978) hypothesises that in relation to their cryptic and slow moving habits arboreal folivores do not live in large social groups. During this study, *P. philippensis* was usually sighted alone. Analysis of the different age classes of squirrels sighted revealed that adult and juveniles tended to be sighted alone, and only animals in the youngest age class tended to be found with a conspecific. This was usually a conspecific in the same age group. *P. philippensis* was also observed vocalising, especially soon after exit from the nest. Arboreal folivores are believed to have well developed communication mechanisms for localising their positions in relation to one another. The calls might have been territorial calls, or contact calls. Further research is required before the reason for these calls can be ascertained. Certain individuals reacted strongly to the presence of the observer and the call emitted was of a slightly higher pitch than usual, this probably being an alarm call. *P. f. fuscocapillus* was mostly encountered alone, and no observations on social interactions could be made. Little is known of the behaviour and social systems of flying squirrels in India, and further research is required in order to understand the social system of the species.

7. HUNTING PRESSURES AND LOCAL AWARENESS

Hunting pressures

During the survey an attempt was made to ascertain if there were any hunting pressures on the study species. It was ascertained that flying squirrels were hunted, though not hunted for commercial purposes. They were hunted mainly for the meat, and not for any other body part. The skin is not valued and is usually discarded. Though both species of flying squirrels were hunted in various forest areas of the Western Ghats, the large brown flying squirrel is preferred as it is larger and provides more meat. The small Travancore flying squirrel is not hunted as often as the larger species. Details of hunting techniques and pressures at each site can be found in Appendix 1.

It had been hypothesized that the hollow nesting and nocturnal habits of flying squirrels have made them less susceptible to poaching (Muul and Lim 1978). However, during this study, subsistence hunting of flying squirrels was seen to be widespread, and flying squirrels are favored to an extent as a food item because they are relatively easy to hunt. The methods used to hunt flying squirrels can be broadly classified into diurnal hunting and nocturnal hunting. Hunting during the day necessitates prior knowledge of the roost site of the flying squirrel. A variety of methods is then used to hunt the animal. The animal might be flushed out of its hollow (either by knocking on the trunk of the tree, or by lighting a fire at the base of the tree) and then knocked down with a stone or with arrows as it tries to escape. Alternatively, the hunter might climb the tree and corner or incapacitate the animal in the hollow, either by lighting a fire at/ in the hollow, or by hitting the animal with a heavy instrument. When the animal is hunted at night, eyeshine is used to locate the animal, and a gun or arrows and stones are used to kill the animal. Once the patagium is hit, the animal is incapacitated and is easy prey.

Table 7.1: Reports of hunting pressures of flying squirrels in areas surveyed.

	number of areas surveyed	<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>					<i>P. philippensis</i>				
		Squirrel not sighted	No information	Past hunting	No hunting	Hunting	Squirrel not sighted	No information	Past hunting	No hunting	Hunting
All Areas	27	22	3	2	2	5	3	12	8	6	9
Protected Areas	15	12	2	1	1	0	1	9	4	3	2
Less Protected Areas	12	10	1	1	1	5	2	3	4	3	7

In 3 sites where *P.f.fuscocapillus* was reported to be present, it was not possible to obtain any information regarding threats to the species. In 12 of the sites where *P. philippensis* was reported to be present, no information regarding hunting pressures was obtained. Out of the areas where it was possible to obtain information on the threats to the species, it was observed that *P. philippensis* was hunted in 33.33% (9) of the sites surveyed, while *P. f. fuscocapillus* was hunted in 18.52 % (5) of the sites surveyed. *P. f. fuscocapillus* was recorded as being poached only in Less Protected areas. While *P. philippensis* was recorded as being hunted in both Protected areas and Less Protected areas, it was hunted more in Less Protected areas (it was reported as being hunted only in two of the Protected areas). In the Protected areas where it was being hunted, it was hunted by tribals for subsistence. One of these reports of hunting was at the border of the sanctuary, where the forest abuts human settlements. There was no hunting reported in the core areas of the Sanctuary. In other protected areas, stringent regulations were responsible for the absence of hunting, and flying squirrels were reportedly hunted in these areas prior to their enforcement. Certain studies have revealed that hunting pressure is lower in protected forest areas with hunting regulations than in non protected forests. Carrillo *et al*

(2000) report that the species traditionally preferred by hunters were less abundant outside a Costa Rican protected area than within it, due to differential hunting regulations in the two areas. Glanz (1991) also reported lower sightings of mammals in hunted areas in Panama.

Tropical forests have traditionally been a source of food for local forest people (Robinson and Redford 1991 in Carrillo *et al* 2000), and are increasingly also a source of food for colonists and settlers near forest areas (Escamilla *et al* 2000). This was seen to be true in Kerala, where hunting is not merely practiced by tribal people in forests, but also by villagers and people in small towns neighboring forests. When hunting was reported in sanctuaries, it was mainly need based hunting by tribal forest dwellers, and it is possible that such hunting does not affect populations of animals. Studies have reported that subsistence harvesting of the woolly monkey and peccaries (Alvard *et al* 1997) and squirrels, duikers and elephant shrews (Fitzgibbon *et al* 1995) was not found to be unsustainable.

The purposes and modes of hunting might cause populations of species to react in different ways. Shotgun hunters drastically depleted local populations of primates while bow hunters killed monkeys in sustainable quantities in Amazonia (Alvard *et al* 1995). Hunting by villagers around forest reserves (Muchaal and Ngandjui 1999) and in forest fragments (Cullen *et al* 2000) was seen to nearly extirpate several species of mammals. At Kannavam, no flying squirrels were sighted in the patch of forest near the township, and local residents explained that hunting had exterminated the population from the surrounding forests. Hunting in places outside forest areas might not be purely for subsistence purposes, and might be fuelled by the need for recreation.

Hunting was also recorded more in Kerala than in Tamil Nadu. The people of Kerala might have a greater traditional reliance on wildlife than people in Tamil Nadu, and this might be related to the presence of more forest cover in Kerala.

Reliable information on hunting activity was obtained with difficulty, as local people were reluctant to divulge information. The accompanying field guides were usually relied upon to obtain hunting information at most sites. The wariness on the parts of the respondents might have undermined the actual level of poaching, and the information above documents trends rather than absolute figures.

Local awareness

The species are known by different names locally:

P. philippensis: Malayalam - paran, parachathan, parayan.
Tamil - paradu, mayapoonai.

P. f. fuscocapillus: Malayalam - poomparan, iliparan, moochink.
Tamil – poonjiri paran.

At most sites locals were aware of the presence of one species of flying squirrel, the large brown flying squirrel. Knowledge of the Small Travancore flying squirrel was limited to a few sites. It was also observed that local awareness of flying squirrels was high in places where hunting was either prevalent or had once been prevalent. The most detailed and accurate descriptions of the species were recounted by people who were either hunters or who had once been hunters. The species being nocturnal and cryptic, there is little opportunity to sight them in the daytime, and this might limit local awareness of flying squirrels. Where there was awareness of the two species, locals distinguished the two primarily based on the size and color of the animals. *P. philippensis* was invariably described as being large and black in color, while *P. f. fuscocapillus* was described as smaller in size and grey in color. The animals were also described to have different calls, and the call of *P. philippensis* was described as being a loud monotonous cry. The call of *P. f. fuscocapillus* was described as a short squeak, similar to that of a mouse. On one occasion a call was heard while recording observations on *P. f. fuscocapillus*, and this call was similar to a high pitched squeak, distinctly different from the call of *P. philippensis*. Locals also described the two species as occurring in different habitats, and *P. f. fuscocapillus* was described as being confined to interior forests.

P. philippensis was also rumored to have medicinal properties. At two different locations, locals described the animal as being beneficial for breathing problems. The meat of the animal is believed to enable one to overcome difficulties in climbing slopes. The blood of *P. philippensis* is recommended for people who are weak, and is particularly given to children. The rationale behind this is that the frugivorous and folivorous habits of the animal cause it to accumulate “oushadis” or beneficial elements, and its meat therefore contains medicinal properties.

Summarizing the results of the questionnaire survey, it is observed that local people are aware of flying squirrels in most places. More people are aware of the presence of the large brown flying squirrel than of the smaller species of flying squirrel, possibly indicating that the large species is more common. Flying squirrels, especially *P. philippensis*, form part of the diet of people in many areas. However, this hunting might not be unsustainable. Hunting for subsistence purposes might not deplete populations, and this has been seen in other studies. Further studies are needed before any conclusive statements regarding this can be made. It is clear from the survey that greater protection status of an area implies more protection to the species within the area. In almost all protected areas surveyed it was seen that hunting had reduced or ceased after enforcement of regulations.

8. THE DISTRIBUTION OF FLYING SQUIRRELS IN THE WESTERN GHATS: AN ANALYSIS.

The Western Ghats have been increasingly fragmented, with a loss of 25.6% of the forest cover in the last two decades (Jha *et al* 2000). The rate and extent of deforestation has however not been even across regions within the Western ghats, and Jha *et al* (2000) demonstrate that some districts have lost more forest cover than others. The occurrence of flying squirrels (examination of both previous records and the results of the survey) over the Western Ghats has been examined in relation to forest cover in different regions in Kerala and Tamil Nadu based on forest cover estimates by Jha *et al* (2000).

In the Kerala regions of the Western Ghats, there has been a substantial decrease in Evergreen and Semi-evergreen forest cover (41 %) and an increase in deciduous forest cover (7.5 %) since 1973 (Prasad 1998). *P. f. fuscocapillus*, described as inhabiting only lowland and montane Evergreen forests (Hilton-Taylor 2000) of Travancore (present day Kerala), might have been affected by this rapid change in forest cover. The low encounter rate and infrequent sightings of the species suggested that it occurs at lower densities than *P. philippensis* and information obtained locally regarding the presence of the species was also used to determine the possible distribution of the species.

P. f. fuscocapillus and *P. philippensis* have been reported to occur in the forests of the Tirunelveli North division (Srinivasan 1977) and Kalakad Mundanthurai Tiger Reserve (KMTR) (Johnsingh 2001) in the Agasthyamalai hills. The presence of both species has been documented in the Quilon and Pathanamthitta districts of Kerala (Menon 1964), which contain part of the Agasthyamalai and Pandalam hill ranges. *P. f. fuscocapillus* was collected after a period of almost 100 years in a coconut plantation in Pattanamthitta (Kurup 1980), 24 km from Ranni Reserve Forest. During this survey it was encountered in Shendurny WLS and Achankovil RF, while *P. philippensis* was encountered in all the areas sampled in these parts (Achankovil RF, Neyyar WLS, Peppara WLS, Shendurny WLS and KMTR). The forest cover in Quilon district has increased since 1973, and the area under plantations has decreased. While the deciduous forest cover and the areas under plantations in Pattanamthitta, have increased since 1961, the area under Evergreen forest has decreased (Prasad 1998). The Agasthyamalai hill complex, encompassing KMTR, Neyyar WLS, Peppara WLS, Shendurny WLS, and forests of Thenmala division, is among the most compact forest tracts in South India (Nair 1991).

The revenue district Idukki has the most dense forest cover in Kerala. However, while the total extent of dense forest cover (forest with canopy > 40%) has increased since 1973, primarily due to protection of forest lands, there has also been a substantial increase in the extent of plantations and agricultural land in the district at the cost of open canopy forest. Both *P. philippensis* and *P. f. fuscocapillus* were encountered in this district. Relict populations of wild animals might continue to exist in areas that are not completely altered by habitat changes (eg. plantations where the overstory is left intact might allow arboreal mammals to continue to exist). In the cardamom plantations at Kootakuzhy, the overstory is retained as shade, and both species of flying squirrels occur in these plantations. At Munnar, *P. philippensis* was sighted in cardamom plantations, which was possibly Evergreen forest before conversion to cardamom. In Thattekad Bird Sanctaury, both species of flying squirrels occur in the teak plantations and degraded moist deciduous forests along the riverbank, habitat that has been converted to plantations from evergreen and riparian forests. *P. philippensis* occurs in a wide variety of habitats and was encountered in most habitats sampled though was most reported from Shola forests in Eravikulam. *P. f. fuscocapillus* was also seen to occur in Evergreen forests in other areas sampled in the district: Knacherry Reserve forest and Periyar Tiger Reserve, which is contiguous with Ranni Reserve Forest.

The districts of Trichur, Palaghat and Coimbatore have experienced the highest rate of dense forest loss (Jha *et al* 2000). Increase in the area under plantations and agriculture and construction of a large number of roads and dams have fragmented the continuity of climax forests. Both species however were seen to occur in these districts. *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered in the Evergreen forests of

the Anamalai hills, (Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary), and is reported to occur in the forests near Athirampally (Chalakkudy RF). *P. f. fuscocapillus* was not encountered in Moist Deciduous patches in this area. The Anamalai hills were once the largest contiguous rain forests in the Western Ghats

(Umapathy and Kumar 2000b), and fragmentation has probably restricted the range of this species to a few patches alone. *P. philippensis* was encountered in all forest areas surveyed. The encounter rate of the species was high in the Moist Deciduous forests in Chalakuddy RF.

North of the Palghat gap, forest extends north to the Bramhagiris along the Karnataka border. There have been few records of *P. f. fuscocapillus* in this region, and the only record of this species is in the Nilgiris District Gazetteer, which describes it as occurring in the Nilgiris. *P. philippensis* was sighted in many of the forests above the Palghat Gap, (Silent Valley NP, Nilgiris North Division, Wynad Wildlife Sanctuary). *P. f. fuscocapillus* was not sighted in these forests, though the species is reported to exist in some of the forest patches. Both species of flying squirrels also occur in Aralam Wildlife Sanctuary and in Kannavam Reserve Forest in Kannur district, though only *P. philippensis* was encountered at these places during this survey. Dense forest cover has decreased over the past two decades in Wynad and Palakkad districts (Jha *et al* 2000), and the forests of Wynad are also badly fragmented (Nair 1991). It was also observed during the survey that the certain forests in Kannur district were fragmented and subjected to high human pressure and this has led to the decline of the species in certain fragments (refer Chapter 7 for details).

Regarding the distribution of the species, this survey revealed that *P. f. fuscocapillus* is more restricted in distribution than *P. philippensis*. Though the distribution of the species is restricted to a few forest areas, it was seen to occur in reasonable numbers in stands that it inhabited. In Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary, the species was encountered in numbers equal to *P. philippensis* in the forest patches that it occurred in, suggesting that though its distribution might be confined to certain areas, it might not be too rare within the patch itself. The distribution of the species might be affected by the loss of forest cover and degradation, as was seen in Kannur. *P. philippensis* was encountered at most sites and across a variety of habitat types. It was also encountered in moderately disturbed sites, suggesting that it might be more tolerant to habitat disturbance than *P. f. fuscocapillus*.

9. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

P. philippensis was encountered more frequently than *P. f. fuscocapillus*. While *P. philippensis* is widespread in distribution, occurring in a variety of habitats and across a range of altitudes, *P. f. fuscocapillus* was encountered only in a few habitats and elevation zones. The results of the survey implies that *P. f. fuscocapillus* is rare in distribution, and is probably restricted to a few habitat types.

It was also seen from the results of the study that the occurrence of flying squirrels in certain habitats might be influenced to a large extent by characteristics of the habitat. The two species were seen to occur in tall mature stands, and *P. philippensis* was seen to prefer less dense stands. The two species were also occupied separate niches, in terms of height and habitat, and probably in terms of food consumed.

Recommendation for further study:

1. Collection of additional information.
 - a. A priority is the documentation of the distribution of the two species across the rest of the Western Ghats (Karnataka, Maharashtra, Goa).
 - b. Examination of habitat utilisation by *P. f. fuscocapillus*. To examine if the occurrence of the species is different in Evergreen forests and Moist Deciduous forests, and to ascertain whether the species occurs only in those Moist Deciduous forests that are relicts of Evergreen forests of the past.
 - c. Analysis of habitat parameters, such as height of tree strata, and density of trees, and the occurrence of the two species.
 - d. An explanation for the syntopic occurrence of the two species, and how they partition resources effectively: utilisation of space and resources by the two species.
2. Protection of the species.
 - a. Analysis of the effects of hunting, and to document if recreational hunting of the two species occurs at any site.
 - b. To assess the impact to subsistence hunting on the species.
 - c. To understand how the species copes with consistent hunting: to study the species at two site; with and without hunting pressures and compare their ecology and reproductive cycles.
3. Increasing awareness of the two species.
 - a. Collection and lodging of skins at a few Museums, so that identification of the species is made easier.
 - b. Increasing awareness of the species with the forest department staff, and encouraging reports of sightings, particularly of *P. f. fuscocapillus*.

Plate 1: Images of *Petaurista philippensis* -top row: ZSI museum samples; lower row: a rescued animal

Plate 2 Top row: *P. f. Fuscocapillus* (left) and *P. philippensis* (right) from museums, lower two images: *P. f. fuscipallus* at Thatekkad WLS

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PLATE LEGEND

Plate 1: Page 36

1. Skin of *P. f. fuscocapillus* at Zoological Survey of India, Calicut. Collected by Dr. G. U. Kurup at Vennikulam, Pattanamthitta district, Kerala in 1987
2. Skin of *P. philippensis* at the Museum, Periyar Tiger Reserve
3. *P. f. fuscocapillus* at the Thattekad Zoo, Thattekad Bird Sanctuary. Note yellowish white cheeks, pale underside.
4. Yellowish white colour on the underside of *P. f. fuscocapillus* continues from underside up to cheeks. Yellowish cream colour underside is distinctive, feet are not black, tail is not black in colour.

PLATE 2: page 37

5. Skin of *P. philippensis* in Thattekad Bird Sanctuary. Note that the colour of the animal is different from the colour of the animal in photo 2 and photo 5. A lot of variation in coat colour was observed in different sites during the survey.
6. Young of a large brown flying squirrel (*P. philippensis*) at Periyar Tiger Reserve, Kerala. Note colour of the cheeks is greyish, and the feet are black.
7. *P. philippensis* in captivity. Note large size of the animal, long black tail, grey cheeks, black feet. Underside is whitish grey, and the colour is different from that of *P. f. fuscocapillus*
8. *P. philippensis* in captivity. Note that the back of the animal is grizzled with grey. The black on the tail does not begin from the base, but from a certain distance after the base.

APPENDIX 1

Table A1.1: Sampling effort (km. walked) across vegetation types and survey sites.

Name of Site	Evergreen	Molst Deciduous	Shola	Dry	Plantation	Km. walked per site
Kalakad-Mundanthurai TR	12.6	-	-	4	-	16.6
Neyyar WLS	-	1.5	-	2.6	-	4.1
Peppara WLS	3.2	-	1.7	-	-	4.9
Shendumy WLS	-	5	-	-	-	5
Achankovil RF	4	-	-	-	-	4
Ranni RF	11.5	-	-	-	-	11.5
Periyar Tiger Reserve	-	16.5	-	-	-	16.5
Idukki - KFDC plantation	-	-	-	-	2	2
Idukki WLS	11	-	-	-	-	11
Munnar	-	-	7.4	-	1	8.4
Munnar – Kuttampuzha	3.5	-	-	-	-	3.5
Thattakad BS	-	2	-	-	-	2
Ernakulam	-	-	-	-	3	3
Pooyankutty	0.6	-	-	-	-	0.6
Kodaikanal RF	-	-	8.1	-	-	8.1
Chalakydy RF	3.1	7	-	-	1.3	11.4
Indira Gandhi WLS	25.7	4.4	-	-	2.4	32.5
Parambikulam WLS	-	5.6	-	-	-	5.6
Dindigul RF	-	5	-	-	-	5
Mannarkad	-	10	-	-	-	10
Silent Valley NP	8.3	-	-	-	9	17.3
Nilgiris	-	-	3.8	-	-	3.8
Nilgiris –Gedde	-	1	-	-	-	1
Nilgiris –Kothagiri	-	-	6.1	-	-	6.1
Wynad WLS	-	7.1	-	2	-	9.1
Kannavam RF	1	-	-	-	-	1
Aralam WLS	-	2	-	-	-	2
TOTAL	84.5	67.1	27.1	8.6	18.7	206

Table A1.2: Sampling effort (km. walked) across altitude zones and survey sites.

Name of Site	0-500 m	500-1000 m	1000-1500 m	1500-2000 m	2000 + m	Km. walked per site
Kalakad-Mundanthurai TR	3	6.8	6.8	-	-	16.6
Neyyar WLS	2.6	1.5	-	-	-	4.1
Peppara WLS	-	3.2	1.7	-	-	4.9
Shendumy WLS	5	-	-	-	-	5
Achankovil RF	4	-	-	-	-	4
Ranni RF	3	8.5	-	-	-	11.5
Periyar Tiger Reserve	-	16.5	-	-	-	16.5
Idukki - KFDC plantation	-	2	-	-	-	2
Idukki WLS	-	11	-	-	-	11
Munnar	-	-	2	5.8	0.6	8.4
Munnar – Kuttampuzha	3.5	-	-	-	-	3.5
Thattekad BS	2	-	-	-	-	2
Ernakulam	3	-	-	-	-	3
Pooyankutty	0.6	-	-	-	-	0.6
Kodaikanal RF	-	-	-	2.4	5.7	8.1
Chalakudy RF	8	3.4	-	-	-	11.4
Indira Gandhi WLS	0.6	19.8	6.1	6	-	32.5
Parambikulam WLS	2	3.6	-	-	-	5.6
Dindigul RF	-	5	-	-	-	5
Mannarkad	10	-	-	-	-	10
Silent Valley NP	-	17.3	-	-	-	17.3
Nilgiris	-	-	-	1.7	2.1	3.8
Nilgiris –Gedde	-	1	-	-	-	1
Nilgiris –Kothagiri	-	-	-	6.1	-	6.1
Wynad WLS	-	9.1	-	-	-	9.1
Kannavam RF	1	-	-	-	-	1
Aralam WLS	2	-	-	-	-	2
TOTAL	50.3	108.7	16.6	22	8.4	206

Table A1.3: Sampling effort (km walked) across vegetation types and altitude zones.

Vegetation type	0-500 m	500-1000 m	1000-1500 m	1500-2000 m	2000 + m	Total Km.
Evergreen Forest	12.1	55.9	10.5	6	-	84.5
Moist Deciduous Forest	28.6	38.5	-	-	-	67.1
Shola forest	-	-	2.7	16	8.4	27.1
Dry Forest	5.6	3	-	-	-	8.6
Plantations	4	11.3	3.4	-	-	18.7
TOTAL Km.	50.3	108.7	16.6	22	8.4	206

Table A1.4: Reports of hunting pressures in different locations.

Name of Site	<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>					<i>P. phillipensis</i>				
	Squirrels not sighted	No information	Past hunting	No hunting	Hunting	Squirrels not sighted	No information	Past hunting	No hunting	Hunting
Kalakad-Mundanthurai TR	✓						✓			
Neyyar WLS	✓									✓
Peppara WLS	✓									✓
Shendumy WLS		✓						✓	✓	
Achankovil RF				✓				✓	✓	
Ranni RF	✓									✓
Periyar TR	✓							✓	✓	
Idukki - KFDC plantation	✓				✓					✓
Idukki WLS	✓						✓			
Munnar	✓						✓			
Munnar – Kuttampuzha	✓				?		✓			?
Thattakad BS		✓						✓		
Ernakulam	✓		✓		?	✓		✓		?
Pooyankutty		✓								✓
Kodaikanal RF	✓							✓	✓	
Chalakudy RF	✓				✓					✓
Indira Gandhi WLS				✓				✓	✓	
Parambikulam WLS	✓						✓			
Dindigul RF	✓							✓	✓	
Mannarkad	✓						✓			
Silent Valley NP	✓						✓			
Nilgiris	✓		✓			✓				
Nilgiris –Gedde	✓						✓			
Nilgiris –Kothagiri	✓						✓			
Wynad WLS	✓						✓			
Kannavam RF	✓				✓	✓				✓
Aralam WLS	✓						✓			
TOTAL	22	3	2	2	5	3	11	8	6	9

✓ indicates positive; i.e. presence.

? indicates a possibility of hunting occurring, no positive reports were obtained.

The table above compiles the reports of hunting of flying squirrels at various sites surveyed. These reports are not representative of the quantity or intensity of hunting, but merely represent the presence or absence of hunting practices. Where squirrels were sighted during the survey, either no information was gathered, or information gathered indicated that there was hunting in the past. On some occasions, there was hunting in the past, but hunting is not prevalent in current times. On occasions when hunting is currently prevalent, it was assumed that hunting was prevalent in the past.

APPENDIX 2

KERALA (Areas surveyed arranged alphabetically)

Area: Achankovil Reserve Forest

Map Coordinates: sampled area: 9°06' N and 77°18'E

Protection Status: Reserve Forest, Less Protected Area.

Surveyed Areas: Kottavasal

Forest Type: Moist Deciduous forest, Evergreen forest.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P.f.fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Achankovil	✓	✓	✓

One nest of the Travancore flying squirrel was discovered near the tribal settlement Pallivasal in Moist Deciduous Forest at Achankovil RF. A tribal of the "Girijan" tribe climbed up a tree and flushed a Small Travancore flying squirrel out of a hollow on a tree. The roost site was a longitudinal hollow, located at a height of 17m on the main trunk of the 30 m tall tree. The flying squirrel glided immediately to another tree (*Schleichera oleosa*) 60-80 m away and went into a hollow on the side of the tree trunk. The second tree was 25-30 m tall and the hollow was located at a height of 15 m. As the animal did not search for the hollow before it went into it, it was probably familiar with its surroundings.

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Local residents and tribals are aware of the presence of two species of flying squirrels at the site. The two species are different in color and appearance.

The large brown flying squirrel is found in most parts of the forest, while the Small Travancore flying squirrel is restricted to the interior forests. The Small Travancore flying squirrel is also found at lower densities than the large brown flying squirrel.

Nests: P. philippensis: Up to two to three flying squirrels sometimes occupy one nest hollow. There is usually one young in a litter, which is born in March. *P. f. fuscocapillus*: Two or three individuals are found in a nest hollow. Locals have never seen flying squirrels hoarding food, or taking food back to the young in the hollow.

Threats to flying squirrels: Hunting was prevalent in the past. The large brown flying squirrel was regularly hunted for meat in the past.

Area: Aralam Wildlife Sanctuary

Map Coordinates: 11°35N - 11°59N and 75°46 E -75°56 E.

Size and Location: 55 sq. km in Kannur district.

Protection Status: Protected Area.

Surveyed Areas:

a) Area beyond Guest house.

Altitude: Ranges from 60 m to 1589 m.

Forest Type: The main vegetation types are Southern hilltop tropical evergreen forest, west coast tropical evergreen forest, west coast semi-evergreen forest and west coast semi evergreen *Dipterocarpus* forest. The only protected area of the *Dipterocarpus -Mesua - Palaquium* type falls in this sanctuary.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Aralam	✓	-	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Tribals describe in details the difference between the two species of flying squirrels. One species is described as large and black, while the other is described as small and brown in colour. Both species occur in the Sanctuary but the large brown flying squirrel occurs in most places, while the Small Travancore flying squirrel occurs more in interior forests.

Threats to flying squirrels: Could not be ascertained.

Area: Chalakkudy Reserve Forest

Map Coordinates: 10°17'N – 10°28'N and 76°22'E – 76°32'E.

Size and Location: Located in Trissur district, it is contiguous on the east with Parambikulam WLS, Vazhachal and Nemmara divisions, and on the south with Vazhachal division.

Protection Status: Reserve forest; Less Protected Area.

Surveyed Areas:

- a) Peringyalkuthu
- a) Sholayar
- b) Malakarapara-Sholayar

Altitude: Ranges from 140m – 1116m.

Forest Type: Wet Evergreen, Semi-evergreen and Moist Deciduous forests.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Peringyalkuthu	✓	✓	
Sholayar	✓	✓	
Malakapara	✓		

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Two species of flying squirrels occur. The Travancore flying squirrel is found in forests beyond the Athirampally dam.

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying squirrels (both *P. philippensis* and *P. f. fuscocapillus*) are hunted, as they are pests in cashew plantations adjoining forest areas. They are also pests in Coconut plantations. The animals are shot when they invade private plantations.

Area: Ernakulam

Map Coordinates: surveyed area: 10°15' N and 76°16' E

Protection status: Private land – Less Protected area.

Surveyed Areas: Plantations on either side of backwaters.

Altitude: Sea level.

Forest Type: Plantations and cultivated areas.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Private Coconut Plantation	-	-	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Local residents are familiar with the large brown flying squirrel, and report that in the past flying squirrels regularly visited coconut trees to predate on the coconuts. In the recent years the occurrence of these squirrels has declined, and they are seen only occasionally. It is believed that flying squirrels do not nest near the plantations, (though they used to nest in large trees near human habitation in the past), and only visit the area to feed on the coconuts. Few residents confused flying squirrels with flying foxes, which are found here in large numbers and which also predate on crops.

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying squirrels were hunted in the past. It is rumored that the Travancore flying squirrel was a popular dish served in bars in various parts of Kerala. Flying squirrels are not hunted in the present day, possibly as the population has declined and the squirrels are not found near settlements.

Area: Idukku, Kootakuzhy

Map Coordinates: 09°54' N and 72° 54' E.

Location: Idukki district

Protection status: Forest department plantation: Less Protected area.

Surveyed Areas:

a) KFDC plantation, Ernakulam Region, Kootakuzhy.

Elevation: 600-1100m

Forest Type: Cardamom Plantations. Evergreen Forests of the Thodupuzha range were planted in a phased manner with cardamom since 1975. Dominant natural Evergreen tree species are: *Calophyllum tomentosum*, *Palaquim ellipticum*, *Cullenia excelsa*, *Hopea parviflora*, *Canarium strictum*. The patch is 1500 ha in size and is surrounded by Reserve Forests and settlements.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Plantations	✓	✓	?

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: All information was obtained from an elderly tribal person who reported that two species of flying squirrels occur at the site.

Description: One species is described as being large and black, while the other is described as small. Though there is not much color variation between the two species, the undersides are different in color. The tails are similar in color.

Vocalisation: The call of the large brown flying squirrel is described as a prominent loud call, while the Travancore Flying Squirrel has a high pitch call similar to white mice.

Habits: The Travancore flying squirrel is active mainly at dusk, while the large brown flying squirrel is active after dusk. The Large brown flying squirrel begins to feed as soon as it emerges from the hollow, and calls after a feeding bout, but doesn't call while feeding. The animal is mostly inactive the rest of the night and goes back into its hollow by 5:00 am.

Nests: *P. f. fuscocapillus* - Two or three individuals occupy a nest hollow.

P. philippensis - A hollow is usually occupied by one individual.

Food habits: *P. f. fuscocapillus* - It is known to feed on *Ficus*, fruits and shoots of *Dysoxylum malabaricum*, flowers of *Bombax* sp., and leaves and shoots of many tree species.

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying squirrels, among other animals, are hunted. While both species are eaten, the Travancore Flying squirrel is not hunted much as it gives a very small quantity of meat.

Area: Idukki Wildlife Sanctuary

Map Coordinates: 9°15'-9°40'N, 76°55'-77°25'E

Size and Location: 70 sq. km, Idukky district.

Protection Status: Protected Area

Surveyed Areas:

a)Vagavanam

Elevation: Ranges from about 900m to 1,400m.

Forest Type: Comprises chiefly moist deciduous forest and grasslands, with patches of tropical wet evergreen and semi-evergreen forest. *Eucalyptus grandis* plantations are being raised in some localities by the Kerala Forest Development Corporation, under a grassland afforestation scheme.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Vagavanam	✓	✓	

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: While the watchers are aware of the existence of two species of flying squirrels, they have seen only species (the large brown Flying Squirrel) in these parts. They report of the occurrence of the Travancore Flying Squirrel in Shantampara, a nearby forest area. The Travancore flying squirrel is locally known as "iliparan", "poomparan", or "moochink."

Threats to flying squirrels: Threats were not ascertained.

Area: Kuttampuzha

Map Coordinates: surveyed area: 10°07' N, 76°50' E

Size and Location: Located in Idukky district,

Protected Status: Reserve Forest, Less Protected area.

Surveyed Areas: Pooyankutty

Elevation: surveyed area: 260 m

Forest Type: Wet Evergreen Forests of the *Cullenia - Mesua - Pallaquim* type. Reed beds are also present.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Pooyankutty watch tower	✓	✓	-

Two young and two adult flying squirrels were observed. Both the young squirrels responded to the call of one adult and followed it through the trees.

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Most information was obtained from forest watchers. Two species of flying squirrels occur in these parts. Flying squirrels are found in large numbers and their calls are frequently heard at night. Watchers at Pooyankutty report that *P. philippensis* is a regular visitor to two mango trees close to the watchtower. In March, when the fruits are ripe, flying squirrels remain feeding on the tree for long periods of time. *P. philippensis* has been observed nesting in a hollow in *Artocarpus hirsutus*, and it also feeds on the fruits of the tree.

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying Squirrels are hunted by tribals as well as by other residents. Hunting is mainly for meat. Tribals at Variyam eat flying squirrels and later use the skins to make drums. The meat is sometimes eaten with ragi. Flying squirrels are also hunted in Kadamparai, in the Anamalai hills in Tamil Nadu. While some tribals smoke the flying

squirrels out of their hollows, most others use guns. A torch is used at night to locate the animal, and once eye-shine is seen, the animal is shot down.

Hunting of other fauna: Other fauna that are hunted are Monitor lizards (*Varanus sp.*), Palm Civets (*Paradoxourus hermaphroditus*) (local name: marapatti), Mouse deer (*Tragulus memmina*) and Hornbills.

Area: Kannavam Reserve forest

Map Coordinates: surveyed area: 11°81' N and 75°65'E.

Size and Location: Located in Kannur district.

Protection Status: Reserve Forest; Less Protected area.

Surveyed Areas:

a) Kannavam range

Forest Type: Evergreen forest, Moist deciduous forest.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Kannavam	-	-	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Local residents describe two species of flying squirrels with accuracy.

Description: One species is described as small, while the other is large. The small flying squirrel (Travancore flying squirrel) measure about 15" in length, while the large flying squirrel (large brown flying squirrel) is very large. The large brown flying squirrel is black in color, while the small one is the color of mud, a reddish brown.

Vocalizations: The calls of the two species are different. Locals report that when a tree is felled, a flying squirrel in a hollow on a tree nearby usually calls.

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying squirrels are hunted. The pressure of hunting is quite high. In certain stretches of forest close to the main road and the township, there are no or few flying squirrels to be found. Local residents say this is as the squirrels have been completely hunted out of that particular area. However, the area needs to be surveyed intensively before this can be conclusively stated..

Area: Munnar Forest Division

Map Coordinates: 10° 07' N and 076° 46' E.

Size and Location : 90 ha patch in Idukky district.

Protection Status: Not Protected

Surveyed Areas:

a) Knacherry Forest, Neriya mangalam range.

Elevation: 100m amsl.

Forest Type: Evergreen Forest. This 90 ha patch of forest is a Kerala forestry project involving planting indigenous species, tending of natural regeneration, Soil working, protecting the forest from biotic interference etc.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Knacherry Forest	✓	✓	✓

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Local residents are aware of two species of flying squirrels. They also reported the presence of other fauna: Palm Civet, Small Indian Civet, and Mouse Deer.

Threats to flying squirrels: Hunting with guns is a practice at the site. Flying squirrels are hunted for meat, but the skins are of no value and are destroyed after the animal is consumed.

Hunting of other fauna: Other fauna are also hunted at the site. One shell of the Travancore Tortoise was seen in a hunter's residence. Local residents are reluctant to divulge information. It is believed that other fauna may be hunted as well.

Area: Munnar-Devikulam

Map Coordinates: 9°50'N – 10°16'N and 76°39'E – 77°18'E

Location: Idukki district.

Protection Status: Private land.

Surveyed Areas:

a) Cardamom Plantations, Devikulam

Elevation: 1200 – 2637m.

Forest Type: Shola grassland mosaic. Sampled areas were cardamom plantations, where the understory has been cleared and cardamom has been planted, but where the overstorey is more or less intact.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Cardamom Plantations	✓	✓	

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Large flying squirrels and civets were reported to occur in plantations according to the plantation workers. No flying squirrels are reported in Shola forests, though Giant squirrels occur in the larger Sholas. Flying squirrels have been sighted at Poovar which is continuous with the Akkamalai forests of the Anamalais.

Threats to flying squirrels: It is not known if there are any threats to flying squirrels or other fauna by way of poaching. Deforestation of trees might affect the availability of hollows and this might affect flying squirrels and other fauna.

Area: Mannarkad

Size and location: Kerala Agricultural University Livestock Research station located near Mannarkad.

Protection Status: Not protected area. Belongs to the Kerala Agricultural University.

Surveyed Areas:

a) Kerala Agricultural University Livestock Research Station

Altitude: surveyed area : 60m.

Forest Type: The Research Station has plantations of coconut, jackfruit, mango etc, and pasturelands. Some remnant patches of semi-evergreen and moist deciduous forest remain in certain parts of the campus.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
KAU Station	✓	✓	

Two flying squirrels that were seen at the site looked different in color and much smaller in size. However, the animals moved away before they could be identified.

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Two species of flying squirrels are reported to occur in the forest patches in the research station (Francis Xavier, pers. comm.). Night watchmen know of three common nocturnal animals: Large brown flying squirrels, palm civets and small Indian Civets.

Threats to flying squirrels: Residents from nearby settlements come into the patches of forest to hunt animals (possibly deer). One party of hunters was seen along with their dogs during a night transect. It is not known if flying squirrels are hunted.

Area: Neyyar Wildlife Sanctuary

Map Coordinates: 8°30'-8°37'N, 77°8'-77°17'E .

Size and Location: 128 sq. km in Thiruvananthapuram district. The Sanctuary is contiguous with Peppara Wildlife Sanctuary in the north and with Mundanthurai and Kalakad Wildlife Sanctuaries in Tamil Nadu.

Protection Status: Protected Area.

Surveyed Areas:

- a) Meenmutti
- b) Therrthakara

Elevation: Ranges from about 80m to 1,866 m at Agasthyar Peak.

Forest Type: Southern secondary moist mixed deciduous forests occur in the lower reaches of the Sanctuary and south Indian sub-tropical hill savannahs (woodland) occur in the higher reaches. It is believed that heavy disturbance has reduced climax natural vegetation to secondary vegetation. Southern hilltop tropical evergreen forest is found along the crestline in the highest reaches of the sanctuary. Isolated pockets of intact west coast semi-evergreen forest and riparian fringing forest also occur in the sanctuary.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Meenmutti	✓	-	-
Thirthakara	-	-	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Information was obtained from forest department staff. Locals are aware of flying squirrels, but no further details of species was obtained.

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying squirrels are hunted by tribals for meat, who roast the animal the fire without removing the skin.

Area: Nilgiri Biosphere Reserve

Map Coordinates: 10°50' to 12°16' N; 76°00' to 77°15' E.

Size and Location: 5520 sq. km. The Biosphere Reserve is spread over Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Karnataka.

Protection Status: Protected Area.

Surveyed Areas:

- a) Silent Valley National Park
 - i) Sairandhri
 - ii) Mukkali-Sairandhri (non protected area en route to SVNP)
- b) Wynad Wildlife Sanctuary
 - i) Muthanga Range
 - ii) Kuppady, Chedalayam Range
- c) Nilgiris

- i) Sims Park, Coonoor
- ii) Kothagiri, Longwood Shola
- iii) Konavakarai
- d) Gedde - private farm house and adjoining forest patch.

Altitude: Ranges from 300 to 2,670 m.

Forest Type: Dry deciduous scrub, Moist deciduous forest, Dry thorn and scrub forest, Evergreen and semi-evergreen forest, Shola forests and grasslands, and plantations occur in this Biosphere Reserve.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscicapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Sairandhri	-	-	-
Mukkali-Sairandhri	✓	✓	-
Muthanga	✓	✓	-
Kuppady	✓	✓	-
Sims Park	-	-	-
Longwood Shola	✓	✓	-
Konavakarai	✓	✓	-
Gedde	✓	-	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Residents in Upper Bhavani have never sighted flying squirrels in the surrounding Sholas. Though Nilgiri Langurs and Giant squirrels are known to occur in some Sholas (Bangitappal to Nadugani route), there are no reports of either species of flying squirrels in the Sholas.

When the call of the large brown flying squirrel was played back to the forest watcher at Sims park, Coonoor, he stated that he has heard the call at the site around dusk, though he has not sighted the animal. Flying squirrels were also not known to occur in Longwood Shola, and this survey was the first documented occurrence of flying squirrels in Kothagiri. At Konavakarai and at Kothagiri, there was one sighting each of a small flying squirrel that was slightly different in color from the other flying squirrels (large brown flying squirrels) seen there. The animals were slow and inactive and sat motionless while light was being shone on them. Only the variation in size and color was different from the large brown flying squirrels, the animals did not exhibit other morphological characteristics typical of the Small Travancore flying squirrel. One individual responded to the call of a large brown flying squirrel that was on the tree above the animal. It is believed that this was the young of the large brown flying squirrel.

A local resident reports two species of flying squirrels in the forests adjoining his farm in Kunjapanai, between Kothagiri and Mettupalayam. He describes one species as being small and gray in color, but states that it is uncommon, and is rarely seen in present times. The large brown flying squirrel is still seen regularly. At Kuppady, young large brown Flying squirrels were seen moving together in pairs. At Muthanga, resident tribals at the elephant camp state that the large brown flying squirrel is quite common in distribution, and is regularly seen on the trees around the elephant camp. It is reported only from Moist Deciduous Forest patches and Riverine patches and along roads, and is not found in Dry Deciduous forests. The large brown flying squirrel is reported to occur at Masinagudi, in Mudumalai Wildlife Sanctuary (Narendra Babu, pers. com).

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying squirrels are reportedly occasionally hunted in Mudumalai WLS (Narendra Babu, pers.com.) It was not possible to obtain information regarding hunting and hunting at other locations within NBR.

Area: Parambikulam Wildlife Sanctuary

Map Coordinates: 10°20'N - 10°32'N and 76°35'E -76°51' E.

Size and Location: 285 sq. km in Palakad district. The Sanctuary is contiguous with the Anamalai Wildlife Sanctuary across the border.

Protection Status: Protected Area

Surveyed Areas:

- a) Orukombankutty
- b) Tunacadavu

Altitude: Ranges from 459 m to 1439 m.

Forest Type: Undisturbed stretches of the west coast tropical evergreen and semi evergreen are found along the western parts of the Sanctuary. Extensive teak plantations (over almost 100 sq. km) have replaced most of the natural vegetation.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Orukombankutty	-	-	-
Thunacadavu	✓	✓	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Tribals in settlements near the Sanctuary in the adjoining Indira Gandhi WLS are aware of the two species of flying squirrels.

Threats to flying squirrels: No threats to flying squirrels were ascertained.

Area: Peppara Wildlife Sanctuary

Map Coordinates: 8°34 N -8°57 N and 77°7 E - 77°15 E.

Size and Location: 53 sq. km. in Thiruvananthapuram district. This sanctuary is contiguous with Neyyar Wildlife Sanctuary on its southern border, and with the Mundanthurai Wildlife Sanctuary on its east.

Protection Status: Protected Area.

Surveyed Areas:

- a) Bonnacard
- b) Pandipathu

Altitude: Ranges from 60m to 1717m.

Forest Type: Peppara Wildlife Sanctuary has less than 20 sq km of intact southern hilltop evergreen forest along its crestline contiguous with Neyyar Wildlife Sanctuary. Though the potential vegetation types are Southern tropical wet evergreen forests, west coast semi-evergreen forests, southern moist mixed deciduous forest, reed brakes and south Indian tropical hill Savannah woodlands, the high degree of disturbance has caused the degradation of most climax vegetation to secondary types.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Bonnacard	-	✓	-
Pandipathu	-	-	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Flying squirrels occur in the sanctuary. However it was not possible to get details of the species of flying squirrels found.

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying squirrels are hunted for meat at tribal settlements near Chantangodu, Chemangala, Podikalai and Valiakalai. Kanni tribes roast flying squirrels without removing the skin. It is believed that the blood of flying squirrels has medicinal properties and is beneficial for people who are weak. Bones of the flying squirrels are eaten as a curry.

Flying squirrels are hunted during daytime. Tribals knock the side of the tree, and when the animal glides out of the hollow, they shoot it down with arrows. Alternatively, people wait by fruiting trees at night, shine light on the animal, and aim for the patagium. Once the patagium is hit, the animal is unable to glide, and is easy prey.

Forest Type: Largely Evergreen forest, but disturbed in parts.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Aluvankuddy	✓	-	-
Veliakavu	✓	-	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: A watcher/ guard affirmed that flying squirrels are found at the site but was unaware of the presence of different species of flying squirrels. He described flying squirrels as being medium in size, and black and ash in colour, and weighing upto 2 kgs.

Threats to flying squirrels: *P. philippensis* is hunted for meat by tribals in Aluvankuddy. Tribals climb the tree during daytime and capture flying squirrels in their hollows. At Veliakavu, the other site sampled, it is believed that flying squirrels are hunted by residents for meat.

Area: Shendurny Wildlife Sanctuary

Map Coordinates: 8°48 N - 8°57 N and 77°4 E-77°16 E.

Size and Location: 100 sq. km. in Kollam district. It is contiguous with Mundanthurai Wildlife Sanctuary and is separated from Peppara Wildlife Sanctuary in the south by 15-18 km wide Reserve Forest.

Protection Status: Protected Area

Surveyed Areas:

c) Kattlipara

Altitude: 120m to 1785m.

Forest Type: Well preserved southern hilltop tropical evergreen forests (extending over at least 50 sq. km), Southern montane wet temperate forest, west coast semi-evergreen forest and west coast tropical evergreen forest, and several edaphic subtypes occur in the sanctuary.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Kattlipara	✓	✓	✓

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Local residents are aware of the two species of flying squirrels.

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying squirrels were hunted for meat in the past, but it was not ascertained if hunting occurs in the present day.

Area: Thattekad Bird Sanctuary (TBS)

Map Coordinates: 76° 40' - 76° 45' N and 10° 7' - 11° E

Size and Location: TBS is 25.16 sq.km., located in Idukki district. Forest extends unbroken all the way from Thattekad to Eravikulam National Park in the north east and to the Anamalai Wildlife Sanctuary in the east, though TBS is not contiguous with other protected areas.

Protection Status: Protected Area.

Surveyed areas:

a) Thattekad Bird Sanctuary - Toursim Zone.

Elevation: 35m - 523 m (Njayapilli peak)

Area: Periyar Tiger Reserve

Map Coordinates: 9°16'-9°36' N and 76°57'-77°25' E.

Size and Location: 777 sq. km in Idukky district. It is contiguous with practically undisturbed forest vegetation in the Ranni and Tenmala divisions, forming part of the Konni, Ranni and Gudurkal Reserve Forests.

Protection Status: Protected Area.

Surveyed Areas:

- a) Tourism Area
- b) Mullakudi

Altitude: Ranges from 900 m to over 2019 m.

Forest Type: Periyar Tiger Reserve covers the largest segment of west coast tropical evergreen, southern hilltop tropical evergreen, west coast semi-evergreen, west coast secondary evergreen dipterocarp forest and southern Indain tropical hill savannah woodland forests.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Tourism Zone	✓	✓	-
Mullakudi	✓	✓	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: The local tribal guide provided information on flying squirrels. He knows of the occurrence of two species of flying squirrels.

Description: The Small Travancore flying squirrel is smaller in size and width than the large brown flying squirrel. The Travancore flying squirrel has a shorter tail, and though the two species are similar in color, the Travancore flying squirrel is more gray. Its head is small, and looks more rounded and less flat.

Vocalizations: Both species have similar calls.

The tribal guide had seen the Small Travancore flying squirrel in Manalar, but had not seen it in the Tourism Zone Forests. He believes the Travancore flying squirrel is found in interior forests.

The Museum at PTR houses specimens (skins, stuffed animals, and a specimen in formalin) of the large brown flying squirrels, and a skin of the Small Travancore flying squirrel.

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying squirrels were hunted at a point of time in the past*. In Mlapara, people climbed trees with hollows that were inhabited by flying squirrels and used a stick to hit the animal inside the hollow. The hunter then wrapped a cloth around his hand and removed the animal from the hollow. The cloth is wrapped around the hand as these animals are reputed to have a nasty bite. Invariably, the animal is eaten right at the site. It is roasted and skinned, and the insides are taken out and cooked in curry or other dishes.

Hunting of other fauna: Other animals that were hunted in the past were Spiny dormouse (*Platacanthomys lasiurus*) which is believed to be good for people suffering from asthma. The Travancore tortoise is also considered to have medicinal properties.

Area: Ranni Reserved Forest

Map Coordinates: surveyed area: 9°41' N and 76°75' E

Size and Location: Ranni Division contains 1059.07 sq km of land area, and is located in Pattanamthitta district of Kerala.

Protected Status: Non Protected Area

Surveyed Areas:

- a) Aluvankuddy
- b) Veliakavu

Elevation: surveyed area: 200m – 550 m.

Forest Type: The vegetation types in this Sanctuary are riparian forests along the river Periyar, grading to moist deciduous, semi-evergreen and wet evergreen forests towards the east. Plantations of Teak, Rosewood and Rubber have replaced the natural vegetation extensively, primarily along the river banks.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Thattekad Tourism Zone	-	-	✓

A Small Travancore flying squirrel was observed in a nest hollow on *Tectona grandis* between 1845 hrs and 2020 hrs. The animal was in the hollow with only its head out of the hollow. The animal did not emerge from the nest hollow in all the time it was observed, possibly as it was disturbed by the torch light.

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Information regarding flying squirrels was obtained from a resident naturalist. Both species of flying squirrels are found at Thattekad Bird Sanctuary. a skin of a young *P. philippensis* is lodged in the museum at the Sanctuary. The zoo at TBS had a captive Small Travancore Flying Squirrel as an exhibit in the recent past

P. f. fuscocapillus has been seen to occur in teak plantations and in Moist Deciduous Forest in TBS and is usually seen in the middle layer of the tree strata. Two unsuccessful attempts of predation on *P. f. fuscocapillus* by the Forest Eagle Owl (*Bubo nipalensis*) have been observed (Eldos, pers comm). It is believed that *P. f. fuscocapillus* nests not in hollows but in ferns clumps, where it has been observed foraging, possibly for insects. The large brown flying squirrel is known to feed on the seeds of *Xylia xylocarpa*; it chews out the exterior and consumes only the seeds.

The two species of flying squirrels have not been seen together though they occur in the same habitat. Though the large brown flying squirrel was not sighted during this survey, two large brown flying squirrels were seen by the observer in Moist Deciduous forest in TBS on a previous visit in January 2000.

Threats to flying squirrels: Information regarding hunting pressures on flying squirrels was not obtained.

Area: Wynad Wildlife Sanctuary (WWLS)

Map Coordinates: 76°01' - 76°28' E and 11° 35' - 11°58'N

Size and Location: WWLS is 344 sq.km., located in Wynad district. Its is surrounded by forest, with Nagarhole NP to the north, Gudalur and Wynad division to the south, Mudumalai WLS to the east, and Wynad South division to the west.

Protection Status: Protected Area.

Surveyed areas:

- a) Muthanga
- b) Kuppady

Elevation: 900 m - 1500 m

Forest Type: Moist Deciduous, Dry Deciduous, bamboo brakes and swampy grasslands.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Muthanga	✓	✓	-
Kuppady	✓	✓	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Locals are aware of one species of flying squirrel, but do not know of the existence of the smaller species.

Threats to flying squirrels: Could not be ascertained.

TAMIL NADU (Areas surveyed arranged alphabetically)

Area: Dindugul Reserve forest

Map Coordinates: coordinates of district: 10°17' –10°28' N and 77°18' – 77°46'E.

Size and Location: In Dindigul District of Tamil Nadu, bordered by Kodaikanal Forest Division to the south.

Protected Status: Reserve Forest; Less Protected area.

Surveyed Areas:

a) Siruvattukadukombai

Altitude: 300m – 2200 m.

Forest Type: Moist deciduous, Shola grassland, dry deciduous, and scrub forest.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscicapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Siruvattukadukombai	-	✓	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Palar tribals have knowledge of flying squirrels about know of one species only.

Threats to flying squirrels: Tribals used to consume flying squirrels up to four years back. They believe it is especially good for curing breathing problems, and it is recommended for people who find it difficult to climb slopes. They reason that this is so as it feeds on a variety of fruits in the forest, and therefore is rich in medicinal properties.

Area: Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary

Map Coordinates: 10°24'N -10°54'N and 76°44'E -77°48'E.

Size and Location: 987 sq. km in size, bordered by Kodaikanal Forest Division , Parambikulam WLS, and Munnar Forest Division.

Protected Status: Protected area.

Surveyed Areas:

- a) Ulandy range
 - i) Karian Shola
 - ii) Ambulliillam
 - iii) Varagaliar
- b) Manamboly Range
 - i) Manamboly
- c) Valparai range
 - i) Puduthottam
 - ii) Andiparai
 - iii) 36th hair pin bend
- d) Amaravathy Range
 - i) Amaravathy
- e) Grass Hills National park
 - i) Akkamalai

Altitude: Ranges from 220 m to 2513 m.

Forest Type: The major vegetation types include scrub forests, dry and moist deciduous forests, tropical rain forests, and the montane Shola grassland complex. Extensive teak plantations also occur within the sanctuary.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Karian Shola	✓	✓	✓
Ambulliillam	✓	-	-
Varagaliar	✓	✓	✓
Manamboly	✓	✓	✓
Puduthottam	✓	-	-
Andiparai	✓	-	-
36 th Hair Pin Bend	✓	-	-
Amaravathy	-	-	-
Akkamalai, Grass Hills	✓	-	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Kadar tribals at Erumaparai settlement, Top Slip, and tribals at Koomaty report the occurrence of two species of flying squirrels.

Description: One species is described as large and black and the other as small and gray in color. While the large "black" flying squirrel is seen regularly near the checkpost at Manamboly and other places, the smaller species is seen more in interior forests and in dense evergreen patches.

Calls: Kadar tribals report that the two species have different calls and that the call of the Travancore flying squirrel is similar to a high pitched squeak. At Koomaty and Manamboly, no difference between the calls is reported.

Breeding: Both species give birth to young in the tamil month *Chitirai* (approx. mid April - mid May), the same season when Giant squirrels give birth to young. Both species give birth to one young.

Nests: Both species live in nest hollows, and the Travancore flying squirrel has been seen lying in a hollow at a height of 3-4m during daytime. The large brown flying squirrel is known to enlarge hollows made by birds to make them suitable for occupation. They chew the edges of the hollow and spit out the wood to enlarge the cavity entrance. This was reported by people at two different sites.

Threats to flying squirrels: Flying squirrels are not hunted in most parts of the Sanctuary in the present times though flying squirrels were commonly eaten in the past. It is reported that flying squirrels are still hunted in Thekkady and in Kadamparai.

Method of poaching: The hunter climbs the tree and stuffs twigs and dry leaves into the hollow and sets it on fire. The animal is then retrieved from the hollow after it is dead.

Area: Kalakad-Mundanthurai Tiger Reserve

Map Coordinates: 08°25" - 8°53'N and 77°10'-77°35 E

Size and Location: The total area of the Reserve is 895 sq.km. and it is located at the southern end of the Western Ghats in the districts of Tirunelveli and Kanyakumari. The reserve is comprised of two adjacent wild life sanctuaries, viz, the Kalakad Wild Life Sanctuary and Mundanthurai Wild Life Sanctuary both in Tirunelveli district.

Protection Status: Protected Area

Surveyed Areas:

- a) Sengaltheri
- b) Kodayar
- c) Muthuikulivayal
- d) Gudaravetti
- e) Kakachi
- f) Mundanthurai

Altitude: Ranges from 40 m to 1,826 m (Agastyamalai peak).

Forest Type: The following forest types exist: west coast tropical evergreen forest, Tirunelveli semi-evergreen forest (unique to the Reserve), southern moist mixed deciduous forest, dry teak forest, southern dry mixed deciduous forest, Carnatic umbrella thorn forest, southern *Euphorbia* scrub, *Ochlandra* reed brakes.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Sengaltheri	✓	✓	-
Kodayar	-	-	-
Muthuikulivayal	✓	✓	-
Gudaravetti	✓	-	-
Kakachi	✓	-	-
Mundanthurai	-	-	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Large brown flying squirrels are reported to have occurred at Kodayar in the past, but have not been sighted in the patch of forest in Upper Kodayar in recent years. They were often found dead on the roads after having hit power lines while gliding between trees. Locals are unaware of the existence of the Small Travancore flying squirrel. Flying squirrels are reported to occur in the Mundanthurai plateau.

Area: Kodaikanal Reserve Forest

Map Coordinates: 10°7'N – 10°20'N and 77°16'E – 77°45'E.

Size and Location: Located in Dindigul Anna district, bordered by Dindigul Forest Division to the North, and Indira Gandhi WLS and Munnar Forest Division to the west.

Protected Area: Reserve Forest, Less Protected Area.

Surveyed Areas:

- a) Bombay Shola
- b) Kookal
- c) Berijam

Altitude: Ranges from 300-2517 m.

Forest Type: The Upper Palanis have large extents of rolling grasslands and Sholas.

Presence of flying squirrels:

Area	<i>P. philippensis</i>		<i>P. f. fuscocapillus</i>
	Sightings	Calls	Sightings
Bombay Shola	✓	✓	-
Kookal	-	✓	-
Berijam	-	-	-

Local knowledge of flying squirrels: Bombay Shola: Flying squirrels are reported to occur by the members of the PHCC, who have observed the large brown flying squirrel in Bombay Shola. There are no reports of the Travancore flying squirrel occurring here.

Berijam: Residents have not heard of flying squirrels. Though Giant squirrels are present in the area, neither species of flying squirrel is known to be present. The only record of a flying squirrel is when a forest watcher saw an animal glide between two trees in a forest clearing at around 9:00 am one morning.

Kookal: Local resident knows of the occurrence of the large brown flying squirrel (local name: paradu).

Description: The flying squirrel is black or sometimes greyish in color. The tail is long and black.

Threats to flying squirrels: Hunting was once prevalent, when people from nearby towns would come to hunt in Kookal and the adjoining forests. Flying squirrels were hunted for meat. Various other species were also hunted, Mouse Deer, Leopard, Sambar, etc.

APPENDIX 3

An open-ended questionnaire was used to obtain information about flying squirrels from local residents and tribals. Given below is the information obtained with this questionnaire, though the structure and wording of the questionnaire were often different at different sites.

Questionnaire

1. Site:
2. Date:
3. Name of respondent:
4. Has the respondent seen flying squirrels:
5. If yes, how many species of flying squirrels are found at the site:
6. Where has the respondent seen flying squirrels, if not at the site:
7. Details of the two species:
 - a. Color
 - b. Size
 - c. Description of calls
 - d. Food habits
 - e. Nesting habits
 - f. Breeding habits
8. Pressures on flying squirrels:
 - a. Are flying squirrels hunted at the site
 - b. If yes, then why
 - c. What is the technique used to hunt the animals
 - d. Are both species hunted?
 - e. Is the respondent aware of hunting elsewhere
9. Is the respondent aware of other nocturnal mammals?
10. Are there any pressures on other small or medium sized mammals?

APPENDIX 4

Other nocturnal mammals sighted during night transects

No.	Species	Site	Vegetation type	Altitude	Comments
1	<i>Loris tardigradus</i> Slender loris	Knacherry, Kuttampuzha Range	Evergreen forest	100	One animal, foraging
		Muthanga Wynad Wildlife Sanctuary	Moist Deciduous forest	950	Two animals, in bamboo clumps
		Top Slip, Indira Gandhi WLS	Evergreen forest	780	Seen on three occasions, near bamboo, and by the roadside
2	<i>Paradoxorus jerdonii</i> Brown palm civet	Kakachi, Kalakad- Mundanthurai TR	Evergreen Forest	1100	Two animals, foraging together on tree.
		Bombay Shola, Kodaikanal RF	Shola	2050	Seen on three occasions.
		Peringyalkuthu, Chalakudy RF	Moist Deciduous forest	330	Animal seen feeding
		Malakaparra, Chalakudy RF	Evergreen Forest	958	Animal lying on branch
		Konavakarai, Nilgiris - Kothagiri	Evergreen Forest	1800	Seen on occasions,
		Manamboly, Indira Gandhi WLS	Evergreen Forest	760	Lying on branch
3	<i>Paradoxorus hermaphroditus</i> Common palm civet	Achankovil	Evergreen Forest	250	Doubtful sighting of <i>P.jerdonii</i>
		Kottavasal, Achankovil RF	Moist Deciduous Forest	250	By side of road, possibly foraging
		Muthanga, Wynad Wildlife Sanctuary	Moist Deciduous Forest	950	Resting in fork of a tree at a height of 1.5m from ground.
		Mukkali, near Silent Valley NP	Cardamom Plantations	920	On liana tangle overhanging road, at height of approx. 7m from ground.
4	<i>Viverricula indica</i> Small Indian civet	Achankovil RF	Moist Deciduous Forest	200	
5	<i>Platacanthomys lasirius</i> Spiny Dormouse	Akkamalai, Indira Gandhi WLS	Evergreen Forest	1550	